

Perception and Evaluation of Regional and Cohesion policies by Europeans and Identification with the Values of Europe

PERCEIVE

GA nr. 693529

Deliverable 2.1

“Report including the database development and implementation and how it supports all the project WPs”

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the PERCEIVE study's quantitative dataset, drawn from secondary, freely available sources. The general idea of task 2.1 is to develop a database of consistent, comparable and timely available data aimed at collecting, standardizing and analyzing data which supports all the qualitative-quantitative analyses and WPs of the project. This task is connected with Work Package 1, and is to be integrated with the original data collected in this project in task 1.3 (EU citizen survey) on perceptions of structural and cohesion funds and reasons why these funds may or may not be supported¹.

The data presented in this project come from several freely available sources and are at the macro and micro levels of analysis. At the macro level, as this study has a regional focus, we collected data at all available NUTS levels (1, 2 and 3) when possible, always attempting to reach the lowest possible level to provide the most geographic nuance for scholars within the project. The sources of this regional level data are large in part from Eurostat and the EU Regional Policy's webpage 'Data for Research'². At the micro level, we collected Eurobarometer (EB) survey data – both the standard EB, as well as several flash EB's that have a directly relevant focus to the PERCEIVE project. For each survey included in our online database, we provide a PDF file of the questionnaire so as to be able to read all questions clearly. With respect to all macro-level data collected, a full codebook is also provided with a source and description of all variables. Moreover, we provide regional level geo-coding for all micro-level survey data in order to facilitate efficient

¹ We would like to thank our research assistants' invaluable contribution to this data collection. They are Richard Svensson, Anna Khomenko, Marie Dumont and Marco Cox. The author would also like to thank the contributions to the deliverable from the QoG Institute.

² http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/evaluations/data-for-research/

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multi-level analyses or to aggregate micro level data to the regional level. All available regional level panel data ranges from 1990-2015 and survey data from Eurobarometer and Structural Fund expenditures range from the year 2000 onward until the latest year available by the original source.

All data presented here were collected by researchers and research assistants from the University of Gothenburg (UGOT) during the fall of 2016 and the spring and summer of 2017. All data have been collected from their primary sources and merged into STATA files to be used for statistical analyses and other research purposes. As the files presented here are large, they are provided via compressed folders to save space. All data, files and codebooks are uploaded open access to Zenodo in accordance with EU suggestions and regulations.

2. PERCEIVE projects supported by the dataset

The PERCEIVE project is a multi-methods project that incorporates several analytical methods. Many projects however will employ some type of quantitative methods. Aside from originally collected data by individual researchers within the project that serve their research needs specifically, this large database provides all researchers with a general pool of data that can be used in an array of analyses on EU policies, with a focus on Cohesion Policy. In the remainder of this section, we summarize briefly how the dataset can support other tasks in the project.

2.1 Work Package 1

As WP1 is already completed, the dataset presented here has largely incorporated the descriptive data used in tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3.

A first objective of Work Package 1 was to provide a general overview of the implementation of Cohesion Policy in the nine regions that were selected as case-studies for the PERCEIVE project.

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The dataset includes the variables used to describe the regions' economic and social backgrounds as well as the Cohesion Policy interventions that took place in the 2007-2013 programming period.

This comparative quali-quantitative analysis resulted in D1.1, a comprehensive report where practices and methods of Cohesion Policy's implementation in the case-study regions are investigated by means of data analysis and focus groups with Cohesion Policy's experts and practitioners. The overall report includes, as annexes, nine individual case-study reports presenting the regions' contexts, the Cohesion Policy's objectives and financial execution and the regional Managing Authorities' governance systems, which Task 1.2 centers on. A specific section of the individual reports makes use of the Eurobarometer data in order to devise a preliminary picture of citizens' sentiments towards Cohesion Policy and, more generally, of their support to the EU. Such data are included at micro-level in D2.1 and will serve as a direct complement to the original survey drafted and administered by UGOT in Task 1. Researchers who will use the original survey (or any other EB survey we have collected) will easily be able to merge the data with the secondary panel data collected here via the regional and national geo-coding of all individual respondents.

2.2. Work Package 2

In WP 2 there are several quantitative studies that could make use of the data presented here in task 2.1. The spatial analyses in Task 2.2 based on spatial econometrics and multivariate statistical analysis can make use of regional level socio-economic data from the Eurostat files, such as measures of economic development, unemployment, etc., along with aggregated or micro level data on an array of cultural and values data from recent EB surveys in order to facilitate the principle component and other multivariate analyses. Such data support the analysis of the spatial distribution

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of citizens' identification with EU project and perception of RP, and the identification of its individual and regional determinants.

In task 2.3, our data on institutional quality ('European Quality of Government Index (EQI), Charron et al 2014; 2015) along with other socio-economic indicators from the macro-level data set can be used in combination with the latest rounds of the standard EB survey which include a host of questions that attempt to measure the values that citizens associate with the European Union and Europe in general. In measuring support of EU Cohesion policy, the researchers here could use the original survey (task 1.3) and the secondary data from the EU special flash barometers on awareness and support for EU Regional policy provided in the online open access data files.

The secondary data collected by UGOT will allow researchers in 2.3 to understand the determinants of citizens' identification with the EU, their perception on institutional quality, and building synthetic indicators.

In task 2.4, secondary data will support the development of the Logit/Probit model aimed at classifying and ranking the nine case study regions according to the estimated level of citizens' identification with the EU project and the regions' socio-economic characteristics and perception of RP. Tracking identity with EU policies and values over time can be done with the 17 years of EB standard surveys, along with the four years of the special flash surveys on support for regional policies. Also in this case, the researchers in task 2.4 could employ aggregated micro level data to the regional level, or elect to conduct multilevel analyses along with other socio-economic regional level variables.

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In task 2.5, the convergence of EU identification can be measured with the times series dataset and the 17 years of EB survey data. In particular, the regional level socio-economic data and data on the Structural fund expenditure by region are fundamental to support the conditioned convergence analysis aimed at (i) investigating how EU regional disparities (NUTS2 level) evolved over time, in particular in relation to the EU enlargement rounds to Eastern and Central Europe, and (ii) identifying the drivers of convergence/divergence trends, which include both secondary data (e.g. Employment, Education) and the indicator of identification with the EU .

There are several comparable questions on EU support which span most of the 17 years available from which the researchers could base their analyses. Data on Structural fund expenditure by region is also provided since the year 2000, and this could be used to test whether convergence maps out with such expenditures. Other socio-economic factors, such as economic development, unemployment and quality of government can be accounted for over time and across space at the NUTS 1 or 2 level in most cases and NUTS 3 in some cases.

In Deliverable 2.6 to be done by UGOT scholars, the research design is multi-level and explores how the socio-economic status of individuals may lead to support for more economic integration in the EU in some regions, yet not in others. The regional variations that they seek to test are economic development, economic inequality and the level of corruption/institutional quality, all of which are included in the panel data in this deliverable.

2.3 Work Package 3

Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 are mainly qualitative or data gathering projects based on more qualitative methods of data collection, the dataset here might simply be utilized for descriptive analyses when needed.

In tasks 3.4 and 3.5, the dataset could provide a source for measuring several variables included in statistical tests. In particular, the times series survey data of four years (2008 to 2015) from the EB flash barometer surveys could prove useful for researchers seeking to track awareness (and the source of awareness) of EU Cohesion policy over time. That respondents are geo-coded by region could be especially helpful here.

2.4 Work Package 4

As tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 are already completed, the data provided here will mainly serve as a compliment to already gathered data within these three research areas, possibly in future publication within international peer-reviewed journals.

Task 4.4 focuses mainly on policy recommendations, yet could use the dataset for descriptive analyses where needed over time and/or across regions or countries to highlight certain effects of Cohesion policy.

Task 4.5 will employ data collected from both the secondary EU flash barometers surveys of Regional Policy awareness and effectiveness along with the original survey data collected in task 1.3 to compare expert attitudes to those of citizens on EU Cohesion policy. The secondary cohesion awareness data could help for an overview on the case study regions that will feed the initial

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assumptions into the Task 4.5. Several surveys, including the standard EB and the original one from task 1.3 also ask respondents about issues or problems most plaguing their region or country which could be useful for the researchers here. The results of EB regarding the image of the EU could serve as regional proxy for the citizens' perception on the cohesion policy efficiency and could be putted in relation with the discrepancies between citizens' and practitioners' view on Cohesion policy.

2.5 Work Package 5

Task 5.1 and 5.2 are data collection and theory building studies in their own right, yet task 5.3 could well take advantage of the European and value-type identity questions that can be traced over time in the standard EB when looking at Regional Policy discourse.

In addition, task 5.5 will build on the original survey in Task 2.1 which contains several questions specifically designed in order to capture a deeper understanding of European identity if compared to standard and flash EB. This latter will nevertheless employed to track regional/national levels of Cohesion policy awareness and appreciation. Standard socio-economic and governance indicators that could serve as regional context variables can also be drawn upon from the regional panel dataset to be used in tandem with data collected from Task 5.4

2.6 Work Package 6

In this WP, the regional level survey data along with the regional level panel data can serve as contextual/descriptive contextual variables in the development and calibration of the System Dynamics model in tasks 6.1 and 6.2.

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2.7 Work Package 7

As WP7 is about story-telling and project communication to the research world, policy-makers and the public in general, our large dataset presented here can serve as a key asset of drawing in interest to PERCEIVE's work from people outside of the project. By uploading this data in open access so all can download and use it, this asset with help in terms of advertisement and possible create spillovers in terms of attention to other work within PERCEIVE:

3. Content, Codebook and description of variables

3.1 Description of Data files

The PERCEIVE database in the online data contains the following files:

1. Times series, cross section (panel) data at the NUTS 1, 2 and 3 levels from secondary sources, ranging from the years 1990-2015. Data are provided in STATA. A codebook for all variables included in this dataset is found in the next section of this document.
2. Special Flash Eurobarometer data on ‘Awareness of EU Regional Policy’. Four surveys have been collected (years 2008, 2010, 2013 and 2015). Respondents are geo-coded by NUTS 2 (or NUTS 1 in the case of Germany) region so as to be able to merge the regional level panel data listed above. All questionnaires corresponding to each year are also provided in PDF format in the online database, marked by the year. Data are provided in STATA. This data is found in the folder marked “*Cohesion awareness data*”.
3. Standard Eurobarometer survey data, containing attitudes toward the EU, among other registers of questions. Surveys were selected to contain as similar questions as possible to facilitate times series analyses by researchers. Surveys are for 17 years – from 2000-2016. All respondents are geo-coded by NUTS 2 (or NUTS 1 in the case of Germany) in each survey so as to match the regional level panel data listed above. All questionnaires corresponding to each year are also provided in PDF format, marked by the year. Data are provided in STATA, with each file marked by its year. This data is found in the folder marked “*Eurobarometer data 00_16*”

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4. EU Structural Fund Expenditures by region. Regional estimates of Structural Fund Expenditures for each budget period (2000-2006, 2007-2013 and 2014-2020) are provided for NUTS 2 regions. Data separate expenditures made by regional operating programmes (OP's) and total (regional OP expenditures plus national level expenditures). Data are aggregated by budget period and given as total expenditures as well as per capita (based on population of the region in the year prior to the budget period in question) for the sake of more valid comparison. Data are provided in Excel, with each variable marked by a variable name used in the regional panel dataset (see the aforementioned regional data codebook for description of each variable in section 3.13). This data is found in the folder marked "*SF Expenditures by Budget period 00_20*"

3.2 Open Access

All aforementioned data and documents can be freely accessed online according to the EU's 'open access' code. The data files can be found at the following internet address:

<https://zenodo.org/deposit/845349#>

4. Sources

Charron, N., Dijkstra, L., & Lapuente, V. (2014). Regional governance matters: quality of government within European Union member states. *Regional Studies*, 48(1), 68-90.

Charron, N., Dijkstra, L., & Lapuente, V. (2015). Mapping the regional divide in Europe: A measure for assessing quality of government in 206 European regions. *Social Indicators Research*, 122(2), 315-346.

Eurostat regional database: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/regions/data/database>

EU Regional Policy: Data for Research:

http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/evaluations/data-for-research/

Flash Eurobarometer (234). 2008. 'Citizens' perceptions of EU Regional Policy'

Flash Eurobarometer (298). 2010. 'Citizens' awareness and perceptions of EU regional policy'

Flash Eurobarometer (384). 2013. 'Citizens' awareness and perceptions of EU regional policy'

Flash Eurobarometer (423). 2015. 'Citizens' awareness and perceptions of EU regional policy'

5. Codebook and description of variables

*****(see pdf attachment)***

THE EU REGIONAL DATASET

CODEBOOK^a

^aJoint collaboration between the QoG Institute at the University of Gothenburg and the PERCEIVE project.

Scholars who wish to use this dataset in their research are kindly requested to cite both the original source (as stated in this codebook) and use the following citation:

Charron, Nicholas, Stefan Dahlberg, Sören Holmberg, Bo Rothstein, Anna Khomenko & Richard Svensson. 2017. The Quality of Government EU Regional Dataset, version Sep16. University of Gothenburg: The Quality of Government Institute, <http://www.qog.pol.gu.se>

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5

1 Introduction

1.1 The Quality of Government Institute

The QoG Institute was founded in 2004 by Professor Bo Rothstein and Professor Sören Holmberg. It is an independent research institute within the Department of Political Science at the University of Gothenburg. The institute conducts research on the causes, consequences and nature of Good Governance and the Quality of Government (QoG) - that is, trustworthy, reliable, impartial uncorrupted, and competent government institutions.

The main objective of the research is to address the theoretical and empirical problems of how political institutions of high quality can be created and maintained. A second objective is to study the effects of Quality of Government on a number of policy areas, such as health, environment, social policy, and poverty. While Quality of Government is the common intellectual focal point of the research institute, a variety of theoretical and methodological perspectives are applied.

In collaboration with the PERCEIVE project, researchers at the QoG Institute have contributed to this joint project of data collection. It is the aim of the QoG team to update this regional database on a regular annual basis.

1.2 The QoG Data

One aim of the QoG Institute is to make comparative data on QoG and its correlates publicly available. To accomplish this, we have compiled several datasets that draw on a number of freely available data sources, including aggregated individual-level data. The QoG datasets are available in several file formats making them usable in most statistical softwares as well as in Excel.

The QoG Standard dataset is our largest dataset consisting of approximately 2500 variables. For those who prefer a smaller dataset, we provide the QoG Basic dataset, consisting of approximately the 300 most used variables. We also provide a dataset called the QoG OECD dataset which covers OECD member countries and has high data coverage in terms of geography and time.

The Standard, Basic, and OECD datasets are all available in both time-series (TS) and cross-sectional (CS) versions, as separate datasets. In the TS datasets, the unit of analysis is country-year (e.g. Sweden-1984, Sweden-1985 and so on). The CS datasets, unlike the TS dataset, does not include multiple years for a particular country and the unit of analysis is therefore countries. Many of the variables are available in both TS and CS, but some are not. Each variable entry in this codebook specifies in which dataset you will find the variable.

The variables in the Standard, Basic, and OECD datasets are categorized in 18 thematic categories. This categorization should be seen as a guideline rather than a definite classification. Each variable belong only to one category, even though many of the variables can belong to several categories.

On the QoG website we also provide two additional datasets. The QoG Expert Survey (2014) and the QoG EU Regional dataset (2010 & 2013). The QOG Expert Survey is a dataset based on a survey among experts on public administration around the world. The data is available in an individual dataset and an aggregated dataset. The QoG EU Regional dataset is based on a survey among 34,000 respondents and concerns corruption on regional level within the EU.

2 Identification Variables

2.0.1 NUTS0

description

2.0.2 NUTS1

description

2.0.3 NUTS2

description

2.0.4 NUTS3

description

2.0.5 NUTS_level NUTS

description

2.0.6 year

description

3 Description of Variables by Original Data Sources

3.1 Eurostat: Demographic Statistic (Data downloaded: 2016-03-16)

Eurostat: Demographic Statistic The Demographic Balance data collection supplies to Eurostat the first demographic data of the year n-1 by end of June of year n: based on the total number of births, of deaths and of the net migration in year n-1 the total population on 1 January of year n is estimated.

3.1.1 demo_cnmigratn Net migration plus statistical

Net migration plus statistical adjustment. Net migration is the difference between the number of immigrants and the number of emigrants. In the context of the annual demographic balance however, Eurostat produces net migration figures by taking the difference between total population change and natural change; this concept is referred to as net migration plus statistical adjustment. The statistics on 'net migration plus statistical adjustment' are therefore affected by all the statistical inaccuracies in the two components of this equation, especially population change. From one country to another 'net migration plus statistical adjustment' may cover, besides the difference between inward and outward migration, other changes observed in the population figures between 1 January in two consecutive years which cannot be attributed to births, deaths, immigration and emigration.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	692
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.2 demo_d2jan_f Population at 1st January, female

Population at 1st January, female. The recommended definition is the 'usual resident population' and represents the number of inhabitants of a given area on 31st December . However, the population transmitted by the countries can also be either based on data from the most recent census adjusted by the components of population change produced since the last census, either based on population registers.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	28	26	728
1	98	1990	2015	94	25	2442
2	276	1990	2015	245	23	6357
3	0	0

3.1.3 demo_d2jan_m Population at 1st January, male

Population at 1st January, male. The recommended definition is the 'usual resident population' and represents the number of inhabitants of a given area on 31st December . However, the population transmitted by the countries can also be either based on data from the most recent census adjusted by the components of population change produced since the last census, either based on population registers.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	28	26	728
1	98	1990	2015	94	25	2442
2	276	1990	2015	245	23	6357
3	0	0

3.1.4 demo_d2jan_t Population at 1st January, total

Population at 1st January, total. The recommended definition is the 'usual resident population' and represents the number of inhabitants of a given area on 31st December. However, the population transmitted by the countries can also be either based on data from the most recent census adjusted by the components of population change produced since the last census, either based on population registers.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	28	26	728
1	98	1990	2015	94	25	2442
2	276	1990	2015	245	23	6357
3	0	0

3.1.5 demo_d3area_lat Area of a region, land area total, sq km

Land area represents the total land area of the region, excluding the area under inland water; it is expressed in km².

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	25	1990	2015	20	21	515
1	70	1990	2015	52	19	1356
2	199	1990	2015	151	20	3928
3	783	1990	2015	580	19	15072

3.1.6 demo_d3area_t Area of a region, total, sq km

Total area represents the total area of the region including inland waters; it is expressed in km²

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2015	25	24	657
1	99	1990	2015	84	22	2180
2	272	1990	2015	232	22	6039
3	1350	1990	2015	1064	20	27656

3.1.7 demo_d3dens Population density, average population per square km

Population density is expressed as absolute value of the average population per square kilometre. Population density - the ratio of the (annual average) population of a region to the (land) area of the region; total area (including inland waters) is used when land area is not available.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	26	23	646
1	100	1990	2014	84	21	2107
2	273	1990	2014	231	21	5787
3	1370	1990	2014	1060	19	26497

3.1.8 demo_deathd_f Deaths - females

Deaths - females. A death, according to the United Nations definition, is the permanent disappearance of all vital functions without possibility of resuscitation at any time after a live birth has taken place; this definition therefore excludes foetal deaths (stillbirths).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	692
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.9 demo_deathd_m Deaths - males

Deaths - males. A death, according to the United Nations definition, is the permanent disappearance of all vital functions without possibility of resuscitation at any time after a live birth has taken place; this definition therefore excludes foetal deaths (stillbirths).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	692
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.10 demo_deathd_t Deaths - total

Deaths - total. A death, according to the United Nations definition, is the permanent disappearance of all vital functions without possibility of resuscitation at any time after a live birth has taken place; this definition therefore excludes foetal deaths (stillbirths).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	692
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.11 demo_fjanp Population on 1 January - females

Population on 1 January - females. Eurostat aims at collecting from the EU-28's Member States' data on population on 31st December, which is further published as 1 January of the following year. The recommended definition is the 'usual resident population' and represents the number of inhabitants of a given area on 31st December. However, the population transmitted by the countries can also be either based on data from the most recent census adjusted by the components of population change produced since the last census, either based on population registers.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	28	26	725
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.12 demo_frate2 Fertility rate, total

The total fertility rate is defined as the mean number of children who would be born to a woman during her lifetime, if she were to spend her childbearing years conforming to the age-specific fertility rates, that have been measured in a given year.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	26	24	661
1	100	1990	2014	79	20	1984
2	280	1990	2014	218	19	5438
3	0	0

3.1.13 demo_grown_nat Natural change of population

Natural change of population. The difference between the number of live births and the number of deaths during the year. A positive natural change, also known as natural increase, occurs when live births outnumber deaths. A negative natural change, also named as natural decrease, occurs when live births are less numerous than deaths.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	692
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.14 demo_growt Total population change

Total population change. The difference between the size of the population at the end and the beginning of the period. Specifically, it is the difference in population size on 1 January of two consecutive years. A positive population change is also referred to as population growth. A negative population change is also referred to as population decline. The population change consists of two components: natural change and net migration.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	699
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.15 demo_janp Population on 1 January - total

Population on 1 January - total. Eurostat aims at collecting from the EU-28's Member States' data on population on 31st December, which is further published as 1 January of the following year. The recommended definition is the 'usual resident population' and represents the number of inhabitants of a given area on 31st December. However, the population transmitted by the countries can also be

either based on data from the most recent census adjusted by the components of population change produced since the last census, either based on population registers.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	28	26	727
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.16 demo_lbirthhoutb Births outside marriage

A birth outside marriage is a birth where the mother's marital status at the time of birth is other than married.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2013	26	23	633
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.17 demo_lbirthl_f Live births - females

Live births - females. A live birth is the birth of a child who showed any sign of life; the number of live births refers to the number of births excluding stillbirths.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	26	23	649
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.18 demo_lbirthl_m Live births - males

Live births - males. A live birth is the birth of a child who showed any sign of life; the number of live births refers to the number of births excluding stillbirths.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	26	23	649
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.19 demo_lbirthl_t Live births - total

Live births - total. A live birth is the birth of a child who showed any sign of life; the number of live births refers to the number of births excluding stillbirths.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	28	25	696
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.20 demo_mjanp Population on 1 January - males

Population on 1 January - males. Eurostat aims at collecting from the EU-28's Member States' data on population on 31st December, which is further published as 1 January of the following year. The recommended definition is the 'usual resident population' and represents the number of inhabitants of a given area on 31st December. However, the population transmitted by the countries can also be either based on data from the most recent census adjusted by the components of population change produced since the last census, either based on population registers.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	28	26	725
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.1.21 demo_mlifexp_f Life expectancy in age < 1year, female

The mean number of years that a newborn child-female can expect to live if subjected throughout his life to the current mortality conditions (age specific probabilities of dying).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	100	1990	2014	79	20	1975
2	279	1990	2014	216	19	5406
3	0	0

3.1.22 demo_mlifexp_m Life expectancy in age < 1year, male

The mean number of years that a newborn child-male can expect to live if subjected throughout his life to the current mortality conditions (age specific probabilities of dying).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	100	1990	2014	79	20	1975
2	279	1990	2014	216	19	5406
3	0	0

3.1.23 demo_mlifexp_t Life expectancy in age < 1year, total

The mean number of years that a newborn child can expect to live if subjected throughout his life to the current mortality conditions (age specific probabilities of dying).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	100	1990	2014	79	20	1975
2	279	1990	2014	216	19	5406
3	0	0

3.2 Eurostat: Economic accounts

(Data downloaded:)

Eurostat: Economic accounts The European system of national and regional accounts (ESA) provides the methodology for national accounts in the EU. Statistics from regional economic accounts are largely shown for NUTS level 2 regions.

3.2.1 econ_2gdp_eur_hab GDP at current market prices, Euro per inhabitant

Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices in Euro per inhabitant. GDP (gross domestic product) is an indicator of the output of a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries. Calculations on a per inhabitant basis allow for the comparison of economies and regions significantly different in absolute size. GDP per inhabitant in PPS is the key variable for determining the eligibility of NUTS 2 regions in the framework of the European Union's structural policy.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	420
1	98	2000	2014	97	15	1461
2	276	2000	2014	274	15	4107
3	0	0

3.2.2 econ_2gdp_eur_hab_eu GDP at current market prices , Euro per inhabitant in % of the EU average

Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices in Euro per inhabitant in percentage of the EU average. GDP (gross domestic product) is an indicator of the output of a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries. Calculations on a per inhabitant basis allow for the comparison of economies and regions significantly different in absolute size. GDP per inhabitant in PPS is the key variable for determining the eligibility of NUTS 2 regions in the framework of the European Union's structural policy.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	420
1	98	2000	2014	97	15	1461
2	276	2000	2014	274	15	4107
3	0	0

3.2.3 econ_2gdp_mio_eur GDP at current market prices, Million euro

Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices in Million euro. GDP (gross domestic product) is an indicator of the output of a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all

goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries. Calculations on a per inhabitant basis allow for the comparison of economies and regions significantly different in absolute size. GDP per inhabitant in PPS is the key variable for determining the eligibility of NUTS 2 regions in the framework of the European Union's structural policy.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	420
1	112	2000	2014	111	15	1666
2	290	2000	2014	287	15	4312
3	0	0

3.2.4 econ_2gdp_mio_pps GDP at current market prices, Million PPS

Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices in Million PPS (purchasing power standard). GDP (gross domestic product) is an indicator of the output of a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries. Calculations on a per inhabitant basis allow for the comparison of economies and regions significantly different in absolute size. GDP per inhabitant in PPS is the key variable for determining the eligibility of NUTS 2 regions in the framework of the European Union's structural policy.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	420
1	112	2000	2014	111	15	1666
2	290	2000	2014	287	15	4312
3	0	0

3.2.5 econ_2gdp_pps_hab GDP at current market prices, PPS per inhabitant

Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices in Purchasing Power Standard per inhabitant. GDP (gross domestic product) is an indicator of the output of a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries. Calculations on a per inhabitant basis allow for the comparison of economies and regions significantly different in absolute size. GDP per inhabitant in PPS is the key variable for determining the eligibility of NUTS 2 regions in the framework of the European Union's structural policy.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	420
1	98	2000	2014	97	15	1461
2	276	2000	2014	274	15	4107
3	0	0

3.2.6 econ_2gdp_pps_hab_eu GDP at current market prices, PPS per inhabitant in % of the EU average

Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices in Purchasing Power Standards per inhabitant in percentage of the EU average. GDP (gross domestic product) is an indicator of the output of

a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries. Calculations on a per inhabitant basis allow for the comparison of economies and regions significantly different in absolute size. GDP per inhabitant in PPS is the key variable for determining the eligibility of NUTS 2 regions in the framework of the European Union's structural policy.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	420
1	98	2000	2014	97	15	1461
2	276	2000	2014	274	15	4107
3	0	0

3.2.7 econ_2gvagr Real growth rate of regional GVA at basic prices by NUTS 2 regions, % change on

Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices - Percentage change on previous year. GVA (gross value added) is an indicator of the economic activity of a country or a region. It reflects the total value of all goods and services produced less the value of goods and services used for intermediate consumption in their production. Several years ago Eurostat has started to collect real growth rates of regional GVA at NUTS level 2 from those Member States which calculate this already. The indicator is part of the ESA2010 data transmission programme, but the transmission will be obligatory only as from the end of 2017.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	2000	2013	27	14	372
1	62	2000	2013	35	8	484
2	158	2000	2013	86	8	1207
3	1	2013	2013	1	1	1

3.2.8 econ_b5n_eur_hab Balance of prim.inc./Nat.income,net.Euro per inh.

Balance of primary incomes/National income, net, Euro per inhabitant. The primary distribution of income shows the income of private households generated directly from market transactions, in particular the purchase and sale of factors of production. This includes as the main item the compensation of employees, i.e. income from the sale of labour as a factor of production. Private households can also receive income on assets, particularly interest, dividends and rents. Then there is also income from net operating surplus and self-employment. Interest and rents payable are recorded as negative items for households. The balance of all these transactions is known as the primary income of private households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2000	2012	20	11	260
1	93	2000	2012	65	9	844
2	267	2000	2012	185	9	2404
3	0	0

3.2.9 econ_b5n_mio_eur Balance of prim.inc./Nat.income,net.Million euro

Balance of primary incomes/National income, net, Million euro. The primary distribution of income shows the income of private households generated directly from market transactions, in particular the purchase and sale of factors of production. This includes as the main item the compensation of employees, i.e. income from the sale of labour as a factor of production. Private households can

also receive income on assets, particularly interest, dividends and rents. Then there is also income from net operating surplus and self-employment. Interest and rents payable are recorded as negative items for households. The balance of all these transactions is known as the primary income of private households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2000	2012	20	11	260
1	100	2000	2012	83	11	1083
2	273	2000	2012	222	11	2884
3	0	0

3.2.10 econ_b5n_mio_nac Balance of prim.inc./Nat.income,net.Million units of nat.cur.

Balance of primary incomes/National income, net, Million units of national currency. The primary distribution of income shows the income of private households generated directly from market transactions, in particular the purchase and sale of factors of production. This includes as the main item the compensation of employees, i.e. income from the sale of labour as a factor of production. Private households can also receive income on assets, particularly interest, dividends and rents. Then there is also income from net operating surplus and self-employment. Interest and rents payable are recorded as negative items for households. The balance of all these transactions is known as the primary income of private households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2000	2012	20	11	260
1	100	2000	2012	83	11	1083
2	273	2000	2012	222	11	2884
3	0	0

3.2.11 econ_b5n_mio_ppcs Balance of prim.inc./Nat.income,net.Mil.of purch.power st.based on final cons.

Balance of primary incomes/National income, net, Million of purchasing power standards based on final consumption. The primary distribution of income shows the income of private households generated directly from market transactions, in particular the purchase and sale of factors of production. This includes as the main item the compensation of employees, i.e. income from the sale of labour as a factor of production. Private households can also receive income on assets, particularly interest, dividends and rents. Then there is also income from net operating surplus and self-employment. Interest and rents payable are recorded as negative items for households. The balance of all these transactions is known as the primary income of private households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2003	2012	21	9	208
1	101	2003	2012	86	8	857
2	274	2003	2012	228	8	2276
3	0	0

3.2.12 econ_b5n_ppcs_hab Balance of prim.inc./Nat.income,net.Purch.power st.based on final cons.per inh.

Balance of primary incomes/National income, net, Purchasing power standard based on final consumption per inhabitant. The primary distribution of income shows the income of private households generated directly from market transactions, in particular the purchase and sale of factors of production. This includes as the main item the compensation of employees, i.e. income from the sale of labour

as a factor of production. Private households can also receive income on assets, particularly interest, dividends and rents. Then there is also income from net operating surplus and self-employment. Interest and rents payable are recorded as negative items for households. The balance of all these transactions is known as the primary income of private households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2003	2012	21	9	208
1	93	2003	2012	69	7	687
2	267	2003	2012	196	7	1955
3	0	0

3.2.13 econ_b5n_ppcs_hab_eu Balance of prim.inc./Nat.income,net.Purch.power cons.st.per inh.in %of theEUav.

Balance of primary incomes/National income, net, Purchasing power consumption standards per inhabitant in percentage of the EU average. The primary distribution of income shows the income of private households generated directly from market transactions, in particular the purchase and sale of factors of production. This includes as the main item the compensation of employees, i.e. income from the sale of labour as a factor of production. Private households can also receive income on assets, particularly interest, dividends and rents. Then there is also income from net operating surplus and self-employment. Interest and rents payable are recorded as negative items for households. The balance of all these transactions is known as the primary income of private households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2011	2012	24	2	47
1	93	2011	2012	92	2	183
2	267	2011	2012	258	2	515
3	0	0

3.2.14 econ_b6n_eur_hab Dispos.income,net.Euro per inhabitant

Disposable income, net, Euro per inhabitant. The disposable income of private households is the balance of primary income (operating surplus/mixed income plus compensation of employees plus property income received minus property income paid) and the redistribution of income in cash. These transactions comprise social contributions paid, social benefits in cash received, current taxes on income and wealth paid, as well as other current transfers. Disposable income does not include social transfers in kind coming from public administrations or non-profit institutions serving households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2000	2012	20	11	260
1	93	2000	2012	65	9	844
2	267	2000	2012	185	9	2404
3	0	0

3.2.15 econ_b6n_mio_eur Dispos.income,net.Million euro

Disposable income, net, Million euro. The disposable income of private households is the balance of primary income (operating surplus/mixed income plus compensation of employees plus property income received minus property income paid) and the redistribution of income in cash. These transactions comprise social contributions paid, social benefits in cash received, current taxes on income and wealth paid, as well as other current transfers. Disposable income does not include social transfers in kind coming from public administrations or non-profit institutions serving households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2000	2012	20	11	260
1	100	2000	2012	83	11	1083
2	273	2000	2012	222	11	2884
3	0	0

3.2.16 econ_b6n_mio_nac Dispos.income,net.Million units of national currency

Disposable income, net, Million units of national currency. The disposable income of private households is the balance of primary income (operating surplus/mixed income plus compensation of employees plus property income received minus property income paid) and the redistribution of income in cash. These transactions comprise social contributions paid, social benefits in cash received, current taxes on income and wealth paid, as well as other current transfers. Disposable income does not include social transfers in kind coming from public administrations or non-profit institutions serving households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2000	2012	20	11	260
1	100	2000	2012	83	11	1083
2	273	2000	2012	222	11	2884
3	0	0

3.2.17 econ_b6n_mio_ppcs Dispos.income,net.Million of purch.power standards based on final cons.

Disposable income, net, Million of purchasing power standards based on final consumption. The disposable income of private households is the balance of primary income (operating surplus/mixed income plus compensation of employees plus property income received minus property income paid) and the redistribution of income in cash. These transactions comprise social contributions paid, social benefits in cash received, current taxes on income and wealth paid, as well as other current transfers. Disposable income does not include social transfers in kind coming from public administrations or non-profit institutions serving households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2003	2012	21	9	208
1	100	2003	2012	85	9	854
2	273	2003	2012	227	8	2273
3	0	0

3.2.18 econ_b6n_ppcs_hab Dispos.income,net.Purch.power st.based on final consumption per inh.

Disposable income, net, Purchasing power standard based on final consumption per inhabitant. The disposable income of private households is the balance of primary income (operating surplus/mixed income plus compensation of employees plus property income received minus property income paid) and the redistribution of income in cash. These transactions comprise social contributions paid, social benefits in cash received, current taxes on income and wealth paid, as well as other current transfers. Disposable income does not include social transfers in kind coming from public administrations or non-profit institutions serving households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2003	2012	21	9	208
1	93	2003	2012	69	7	687
2	267	2003	2012	196	7	1955
3	0	0

3.2.19 econ_b6n_ppcs_hab_eu Dispos.income,net.Purch.power consumption st.per inh.in %of the EU av

Disposable income, net, Purchasing power consumption standards per inhabitant in percentage of the EU average. The disposable income of private households is the balance of primary income (operating surplus/mixed income plus compensation of employees plus property income received minus property income paid) and the redistribution of income in cash. These transactions comprise social contributions paid, social benefits in cash received, current taxes on income and wealth paid, as well as other current transfers. Disposable income does not include social transfers in kind coming from public administrations or non-profit institutions serving households.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	2011	2012	24	2	47
1	93	2011	2012	92	2	183
2	267	2011	2012	258	2	515
3	0	0

3.3 Eurostat: Education Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-17)

Eurostat: Education Statistics Education statistics cover a range of subjects, including: expenditure, personnel, participation rates, and attainment. The standards for international statistics on education are set by three international organisations: the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) institute for statistics (UIS); the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD); Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union. The main source of data is a joint UNESCO / OECD / Eurostat (UOE) questionnaire on education systems and this is the basis for the core components of the Eurostat database on education statistics; Eurostat also collects data on regional enrolments and foreign language learning. Data on educational attainment and adult learning are mainly provided by household surveys, in particular the EU labour force survey (LFS), which is complemented by an adult education survey (AES) and the continuing vocational training survey (CVTS).

3.3.1 educ_4yo Participation rates of 4-years-olds in education at regional level

Participation rates of 4-years-olds in education at regional level. Number of 4-year-olds who are in either pre-primary or primary education as percentage of all 4-year-olds in the population by region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	26	14	395
1	98	1998	2012	78	12	1173
2	203	1998	2012	140	10	2101
3	0	0

3.3.2 educ_ed25640_2_f Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Less than prim, prim and lower sec educ (lev 0-2)

Percentage of population 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2). Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education: this aggregate refers to levels 0, 1 and 2 of the ISCED 2011 (online code ED0-2). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 0, 1 and 2 but also include level 3C short (educational attainment from ISCED level 3 programmes of less than two years).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	95	14	1431
2	293	2000	2014	265	14	3977
3	0	0

3.3.3 educ_ed25640_2_m Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Less than prim, prim and lower sec educ (lev 0-2)

Percentage of females 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2). Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education: this aggregate refers to levels 0, 1 and 2 of the ISCED 2011 (online code ED0-2). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 0, 1 and 2 but also include level 3C short (educational attainment from ISCED level 3 programmes of less than two years).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1435
2	293	2000	2014	265	14	3981
3	0	0

3.3.4 educ_ed25640_2_t Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Less than prim, prim and lower sec educ (lev 0-2)

Percentage of males 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2). Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education: this aggregate refers to levels 0, 1 and 2 of the ISCED 2011 (online code ED0-2). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 0, 1 and 2 but also include level 3C short (educational attainment from ISCED level 3 programmes of less than two years).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1443
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3989
3	0	0

3.3.5 educ_ed25643_4_f Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Up-sec and post-sec non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)

Percentage of females 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4). Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education: this aggregate corresponds to ISCED 2011 levels 3 and 4 (online code ED3_4). ISCED 2011 level 3 programmes of partial level completion are considered within ISCED level 3. Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 3C long, 3A, 3B and 4.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1442
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3987
3	0	0

3.3.6 educ_ed25643_4_m Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Up-sec and post-sec non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)

Percentage of males 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4). Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education: this aggregate corresponds to ISCED 2011 levels 3 and 4 (online code ED3_4). ISCED 2011 level 3 programmes of partial level completion are considered within ISCED level 3. Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 3C long, 3A, 3B and 4.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1442
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3986
3	0	0

3.3.7 educ_ed25643_4_t Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Up-sec and post-sec non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)

Percentage of population 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4). Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education: this aggregate corresponds to ISCED 2011 levels 3 and 4 (online code ED3_4). ISCED 2011 level 3 programmes of partial level completion are considered within ISCED level 3. Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 3C long, 3A, 3B and 4.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1443
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3989
3	0	0

3.3.8 educ_ed25643_8_f Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Up-sec, post-sec non-ter and ter educ (lev 3-8)

Percentage of females 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1443
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3989
3	0	0

3.3.9 educ_ed25643_8_m Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Up-sec, post-sec non-ter and ter educ (lev 3-8)

Percentage of males 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1443
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3989
3	0	0

3.3.10 educ_ed25643_8_t Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, Up-sec, post-sec non-ter and ter educ (lev 3-8)

Percentage of population 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1443
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3989
3	0	0

3.3.11 educ_ed25645_8_f Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, ter educ (lev 5-8)

Percentage of females 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is tertiary education (levels 5-8). Tertiary education: this aggregate covers ISCED 2011 levels 5, 6, 7 and 8 (short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level, online code ED5-8 Štertiary educationŠ). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 5 and 6.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1434
2	293	2000	2014	265	14	3977
3	0	0

3.3.12 educ_ed25645_8_m Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, ter educ (lev 5-8)

Percentage of males 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is tertiary education (levels 5-8). Tertiary education: this aggregate covers ISCED 2011 levels 5, 6, 7 and 8 (short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level, online code ED5-8 Štertiary educationŠ). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 5 and 6.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	95	14	1420
2	293	2000	2014	264	14	3959
3	0	0

3.3.13 educ_ed25645_8_t Pop.25-64y.o by ed.at.lev.,%, ter educ (lev 5-8)

Percentage of population 25-64 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is tertiary education (levels 5-8). Tertiary education: this aggregate covers ISCED 2011 levels 5, 6, 7 and 8 (short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level, online code ED5-8 Štertiary educationŠ). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 5 and 6.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	100	2000	2014	96	14	1443
2	293	2000	2014	266	14	3989
3	0	0

3.3.14 educ_ed30340_2_f Ed at lev 30-34 years,Less than prim, prim and lower sec educ (lev 0-2),in %,Fem

Percentage of females 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2). Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education: this aggregate refers to levels 0, 1 and 2 of the ISCED 2011 (online code ED0-2). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 0, 1 and 2 but also include level 3C short (educational attainment from ISCED level 3 programmes of less than two years).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	406
1	99	2000	2014	87	13	1300
2	272	2000	2014	212	12	3186
3	0	0

3.3.15 educ_ed30340_2_m Ed at lev 30-34 years,Less than prim, prim and lower sec educ (lev 0-2),in %,Mal

Percentage of males 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2).Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education: this aggregate refers to levels 0, 1 and 2 of the ISCED 2011 (online code ED0-2). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 0, 1 and 2 but also include level 3C short (educational attainment from ISCED level 3 programmes of less than two years).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	99	2000	2014	88	13	1327
2	270	2000	2014	218	12	3267
3	0	0

3.3.16 educ_ed30343_4_f Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec. and post-sec. non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4),in %,Fema

Percentage of females 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4). Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education: this aggregate corresponds to ISCED 2011 levels 3 and 4 (online code ED3_4). ISCED 2011 level 3 programmes of partial level completion are considered within ISCED level 3. Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 3C long, 3A, 3B and 4.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	407
1	97	2000	2014	90	14	1345
2	285	2000	2014	247	13	3712
3	0	0

3.3.17 educ_ed30343_4_m Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec. and post-sec. non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4),in %,Male

Percentage of males 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4). Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education: this aggregate corresponds to ISCED 2011 levels 3 and 4 (online code ED3_4). ISCED 2011 level 3 programmes of partial level completion are considered within ISCED level 3. Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 3C long, 3A, 3B and 4.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	97	2000	2014	90	14	1346
2	285	2000	2014	247	13	3707
3	0	0

3.3.18 educ_ed30343_4_t Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec. and post-sec. non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4),in %,Tota

Percentage of population 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4). Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education: this aggregate corresponds to ISCED 2011 levels 3 and 4 (online code ED3_4). ISCED 2011 level 3 programmes of partial level completion are considered within ISCED level 3. Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 3C long, 3A, 3B and 4.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	99	2000	2014	90	14	1354
2	291	2000	2014	251	13	3766
3	0	0

3.3.19 educ_ed30343_4gen_f Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec.and post-sec.non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)-gen,in %,Fe

Percentage of females 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4) - general.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2014	2014	28	1	28
1	85	2014	2014	85	1	85
2	177	2014	2014	177	1	177
3	0	0

3.3.20 educ_ed30343_4gen_m Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec.and post-sec.non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)-gen,in %,Ma

Percentage of males 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4) - general.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2014	2014	28	1	28
1	84	2014	2014	84	1	84
2	162	2014	2014	162	1	162
3	0	0

3.3.21 educ_ed30343_4gen_t Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec.and post-sec.non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)-gen.,in %,To

Percentage of population 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4) - general.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2014	2014	28	1	28
1	88	2014	2014	88	1	88
2	221	2014	2014	221	1	221
3	0	0

3.3.22 educ_ed30343_4voc_f Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec.and post-sec.non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)-voc,in %,Fe

Percentage of females 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4) - vocational.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2014	2014	28	1	28
1	95	2014	2014	95	1	95
2	256	2014	2014	256	1	256
3	0	0

3.3.23 educ_ed30343_4voc_m Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec.and post-sec.non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)-voc,in %,Ma

Percentage of males 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4) - vocational.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2014	2014	28	1	28
1	95	2014	2014	95	1	95
2	259	2014	2014	259	1	259
3	0	0

3.3.24 educ_ed30343_4voc_t Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec.and post-sec.non-ter educ (lev 3 and 4)-voc,in %,To

Percentage of population 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4) - vocational.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2014	2014	28	1	28
1	95	2014	2014	95	1	95
2	264	2014	2014	264	1	264
3	0	0

3.3.25 educ_ed30343_8_f Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec., post-sec. non-ter and ter educ (lev 3-8),in %,Fem

Percentage of females 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	99	2000	2014	90	14	1357
2	290	2000	2014	251	13	3769
3	0	0

3.3.26 educ_ed30343_8_m Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec., post-sec. non-ter and ter educ (lev 3-8),in %,Mal

Percentage of males 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	97	2000	2014	90	14	1346
2	287	2000	2014	250	13	3750
3	0	0

3.3.27 educ_ed30343_8_t Ed at lev 30-34 years,Up-sec., post-sec. non-ter and ter educ (lev 3-8),in %,Tot

Percentage of population 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary and tertiary education (levels 3-8).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	99	2000	2014	91	14	1367
2	292	2000	2014	253	13	3791
3	0	0

3.3.28 educ_ed30345_8_f Ed at lev 30-34 years,ter educ (lev 5-8), Female

Percentage of females 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is tertiary education (levels 5-8). Tertiary education: this aggregate covers ISCED 2011 levels 5, 6, 7 and 8 (short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level, online code ED5-8 Štertiary educationŠ). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 5 and 6.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	417
1	97	2000	2014	93	14	1388
2	283	2000	2014	250	13	3753
3	0	0

3.3.29 educ_ed30345_8_m Ed at lev 30-34 years,ter educ (lev 5-8),in %,Male

Percentage of males 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is tertiary education (levels 5-8). Tertiary education: this aggregate covers ISCED 2011 levels 5, 6, 7 and 8 (short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level, online code ED5-8 Štertiary educationŠ). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 5 and 6.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	415
1	97	2000	2014	92	14	1387
2	281	2000	2014	245	13	3670
3	0	0

3.3.30 educ_ed30345_8_t Ed at lev 30-34 years,ter educ (lev 5-8),in %,Total

Percentage of population 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is tertiary education (levels 5-8). Tertiary education: this aggregate covers ISCED 2011 levels 5, 6, 7 and 8 (short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level, online code ED5-8 Štertiary educationŠ). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 5 and 6.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	28	15	418
1	98	2000	2014	94	14	1403
2	289	2000	2014	260	13	3898
3	0	0

3.3.31 educ_ed3034_0_2_t Ed at lev 30-34 years,less than prim, prim and lower sec educ (lev 0-2),in %,Tot

Percentage of population 30-34 years old whose the highest level of education successfully completed is Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (levels 0-2). Less than primary, primary and lower secondary education: this aggregate refers to levels 0, 1 and 2 of the ISCED 2011 (online code ED0-2). Data up to 2013 refer to ISCED 1997 levels 0, 1 and 2 but also include level 3C short (educational attainment from ISCED level 3 programmes of less than two years).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	408
1	99	2000	2014	92	14	1376
2	286	2000	2014	242	13	3637
3	0	0

3.3.32 educ_eleav_f Early leavers from education and training, Y18-24,%,female

Early leavers from education and training denotes the percentage of the females aged 18 to 24 having attained at most lower secondary education and not being involved in further education or training. The numerator of the indicator refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who meet the following two conditions:

(a) the highest level of education or training they have completed is ISCED 2011 level 0, 1 or 2 (ISCED 1997: 0, 1, 2 or 3C short) and (b) they have not received any education or training (i.e. neither formal nor non-formal) in the four weeks preceding the survey. The denominator in the total population consists of the same age group, excluding the respondents who have not answered the questions 'highest level of education or training successfully completed' and 'participation in education and training'.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	407
1	99	2000	2014	91	14	1366
2	267	2000	2014	205	11	3068
3	0	0

3.3.33 educ_eleav_m Early leavers from education and training, Y18-24,%, male

Early leavers from education and training denotes the percentage of the males aged 18 to 24 having attained at most lower secondary education and not being involved in further education or training. The numerator of the indicator refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who meet the following two conditions:

(a) the highest level of education or training they have completed is ISCED 2011 level 0, 1 or 2 (ISCED 1997: 0, 1, 2 or 3C short) and (b) they have not received any education or training (i.e. neither formal nor non-formal) in the four weeks preceding the survey. The denominator in the total population consists of the same age group, excluding the respondents who have not answered the questions 'highest level of education or training successfully completed' and 'participation in education and training'.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	407
1	99	2000	2014	92	14	1387
2	278	2000	2014	228	12	3424
3	0	0

3.3.34 educ_eleav_t Early leavers from education and training, Y18-24,%, total

Early leavers from education and training denotes the percentage of the population aged 18 to 24 having attained at most lower secondary education and not being involved in further education or training. The numerator of the indicator refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who meet the following two conditions: (a) the highest level of education or training they have completed is ISCED 2011 level 0, 1 or 2 (ISCED 1997: 0, 1, 2 or 3C short) and (b) they have not received any education or training (i.e. neither formal nor non-formal) in the four weeks preceding the survey. The denominator in the total population consists of the same age group, excluding the respondents who have not answered the questions 'highest level of education or training successfully completed' and 'participation in education and training'.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2000	2014	27	15	407
1	99	2000	2014	94	14	1416
2	287	2000	2014	254	13	3804
3	0	0

3.3.35 educ_rst_ter_ISCED_56 Ratio of the proportion of students (ISCED 5-6) over the proportion of the pop.

Ratio of the proportion of students (ISCED 5-6) over the proportion of the population by NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 regions

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	26	14	397
1	98	1998	2012	87	13	1310
2	205	1998	2012	168	12	2522
3	0	0

3.3.36 educ_st_ISCED Students (all ISCED levels) aged 17 - % of corresponding age pop

Students (all ISCED levels) aged 17 at regional level - as % of corresponding age population

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	26	14	396
1	98	1998	2012	79	12	1178
2	203	1998	2012	143	11	2138
3	0	0

3.3.37 educ_st_ISCED_06 Pupils and Students in all levels of educ(ISCED 0-6) -% of tot pop

Pupils and Students in all levels of education (ISCED 0-6) - as % of total population at regional level

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	27	14	402
1	98	1998	2012	87	13	1305
2	205	1998	2012	167	12	2499
3	0	0

3.3.38 educ_st_ISCED_3 Students at ISCED 3(GEN)-%of all students at ISCED 3

Students at ISCED level 3 (GEN) - as % of all students at ISCED level 3 at regional level

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2004	2012	28	9	248
1	98	2004	2012	96	9	866
2	205	2004	2012	191	8	1722
3	0	0

3.3.39 educ_st_ISCED_56 Students at ISCED 5-6 -%of all pupils and students

Students at ISCED levels 5-6 - as % of all pupils and students at regional level

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	27	14	398
1	98	1998	2012	87	13	1302
2	205	1998	2012	166	12	2488
3	0	0

3.3.40 educ_st_pr_low Pupils in prim and lower second educ (ISCED 1-2)-as % of total pop

Pupils in primary and lower secondary education (ISCED 1-2) - as % of total population at regional level

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	27	14	402
1	98	1998	2012	88	13	1314
2	205	1998	2012	169	12	2529
3	0	0

3.3.41 educ_st_ter_ISCED_56 Students in tertiary education(ISCED 5-6)- % of the pop. 20-24 years

Students in tertiary education (ISCED 5-6) - as % of the population aged 20-24 years at regional level

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	26	14	395
1	98	1998	2012	87	13	1299
2	205	1998	2012	168	12	2517
3	0	0

3.3.42 educ_st_ups_psec Pup and Stud in up-sec and post-sec non-tert educ(ISCED 3-4)-%of the pop 15-24y

Pupils and Students in upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED 3-4) - as % of the population aged 15-24 years at regional level

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	27	14	400
1	98	1998	2012	87	13	1304
2	205	1998	2012	168	12	2524
3	0	0

3.3.43 educ_tst_ter_ISCED_56 Students (ISCED 5-6)- % of tot country level stu-dents (ISCED 5-6)

Students (ISCED 5-6) at regional level - as % of total country level students (ISCED 5-6)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1998	2012	27	14	398
1	98	1998	2012	87	13	1310
2	205	1998	2012	168	12	2527
3	0	0

3.4 Eurostat: Environmental statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-16)

Eurostat: Environmental statistics This relates to any kind of sewage treatment (primary to tertiary) in municipal treatment plants run by public authorities or by private companies (on behalf of local authorities), whose main purpose is sewage treatment

3.4.1 env_ind Independent wastewater treatment plants - total

Independent wastewater treatment plants - total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	7	2000	2013	3	5	35
1	0	0
2	129	2000	2013	31	3	436
3	0	0

3.4.2 env_res_pop Resident population

Resident population.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.4.3 env_urb_cs Urban wastewater collecting system

Urban wastewater collecting system.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	7	2000	2013	2	4	31
1	0	0
2	168	2000	2013	50	4	706
3	0	0

3.4.4 env_urb_oth_nc Share of resident population not connected to urban or other wastewater treatment

Percentage of resident population not connected to urban and other wastewater treatment plants.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	9	2000	2013	5	7	67
1	0	0
2	101	2000	2013	34	5	473
3	0	0

3.4.5 env_urb_oth_t1 Urban and other wastewater treatment plants - primary treatment

Urban and other wastewater treatment plants - primary treatment.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	10	2000	2013	5	7	70
1	0	0
2	120	2000	2013	51	6	708
3	0	0

3.4.6 env_urb_oth_t2 Urban and other wastewater treatment plants - secondary treatment

Urban and other wastewater treatment plants - secondary treatment.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	11	2000	2013	5	7	75
1	0	0
2	125	2000	2013	52	6	733
3	0	0

3.4.7 env_urb_oth_t3 Urban and other wastewater treatment plants - tertiary treatment

Urban and other wastewater treatment plants - tertiary treatment.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	11	2000	2013	5	7	75
1	0	0
2	123	2000	2013	47	5	659
3	0	0

3.5 EQI Data

(Data downloaded: date)

EQI Data description

3.5.1 eqi_eqi EQI 2013

description

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2010	2013	14	2	56
1	41	2010	2013	21	2	82
2	148	2010	2013	73	2	293
3	0	0

3.5.2 eqi_eqi100 EQI10013

description

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2010	2013	14	2	56
1	41	2010	2013	21	2	82
2	148	2010	2013	73	2	293
3	0	0

3.5.3 eqi_margin margin13

description

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	41	2010	2013	21	2	82
2	148	2010	2013	71	2	284
3	0	0

3.5.4 eqi_zrCorr zrCorr

description

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	45	2010	2013	22	2	86
2	148	2010	2013	68	2	272
3	0	0

3.5.5 eqi_zrImpart zrImpart

description

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	45	2010	2013	22	2	86
2	148	2010	2013	68	2	272
3	0	0

3.5.6 eqi_zrQual zrQual
description

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	45	2010	2013	22	2	86
2	148	2010	2013	68	2	272
3	0	0

3.6 Eurostat: Health Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-18)

Eurostat: Health Statistics Total hospital beds are all hospital beds which are regularly main-tained and staffed and immediately available for the care of admitted patients. Total hospital beds (HP.1) are all hospital beds which are regularly maintained and staffed and immediately available for the care of admitted patients. Total hospital beds are broken down as follows: Curative care (acute care) beds; Psychiatric care beds; Long-term care beds (excluding psychiatric care beds); Other hospital beds.

3.6.1 health_dent_hthaba Dentists,Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Dentists,Per hundred thousand inhabitants. Data on dentists should refer to those immediately serving patients, i.e. dentists who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore for some countries the data might refer to dentists licensed to practice (i.e. successfully graduated dentists irrespective whether they see patients or not) or they might include dentists who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	20	20	416
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	191	1993	2013	145	16	3053
3	0	0

3.6.2 health_dent_nr Dentists,Number

Dentists,Number. Data on dentists should refer to those immediately serving patients, i.e. dentists who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore for some countries the data might refer to dentists licensed to practice (i.e. successfully graduated dentists irrespective whether they see patients or not) or they might include dentists who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2014	19	20	418
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	192	1993	2014	147	17	3232
3	0	0

3.6.3 health_dent_p Dentists,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 Dentist. Data on dentists should refer to those immediately serving patients, i.e. dentists who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore for some countries the data might refer to dentists licensed to practice (i.e. successfully graduated dentists irrespective whether they see patients or not) or they might include dentists who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	20	20	416
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	191	1993	2013	145	16	3053
3	0	0

3.6.4 health_hbed_cur_hab_p Curative care beds in hospitals ,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per c1 curative care beds in hospitals

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	401
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	191	1993	2013	150	16	3150
3	0	0

3.6.5 health_hbed_cur_nr Curative care beds in hospitals,Number Curative care beds in hospitals, Number

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	401
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	192	1993	2013	153	17	3209
3	0	0

3.6.6 health_hbed_cur_p_hthab Curative care beds in hospitals ,Per hundred thou-sand inhabitants

Curative care beds in hospitals, Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	401
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	191	1993	2013	150	16	3150
3	0	0

3.6.7 health_hbed_hab_p Available beds in hospitals ,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 available beds in hospitals

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	401
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	190	1993	2013	148	16	3116
3	0	0

3.6.8 health_hbed_lt_hab_p Long-term care beds (except psychiatric) in hospitals ,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 long-term care beds (except psychiatric) in hospitals

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	17	1993	2013	14	18	300
1	0	0
2	158	1993	2013	114	15	2390
3	0	0

3.6.9 health_hbed_lt_nr Long-term care beds (except psychiatric) in hospitals ,Num-ber

Long-term care beds (except psychiatric) in hospitals, Number

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	18	1993	2013	16	18	326
1	0	0
2	172	1993	2013	134	16	2806
3	0	0

3.6.10 health_hbed_lt_p_hthab Long-term care beds(except psychiatric)in hospit,Per 100 thousand inh-ts

Long-term care beds (except psychiatric) in hospitals, Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	18	1993	2013	16	18	326
1	0	0
2	170	1993	2013	131	16	2744
3	0	0

3.6.11 health_hbed_nr Available beds in hospitals,Number

Available beds in hospitals , Number

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	401
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	192	1993	2013	152	17	3191
3	0	0

3.6.12 health_hbed_p_hthab Available beds in hospitals ,Per hundred thousand in-habitants

Available beds in hospitals, Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	401
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	190	1993	2013	148	16	3116
3	0	0

3.6.13 health_hbed_psy_hab_p Psychiatric care beds in hospitals ,Inhabitants per

...

Inhabitants per 1 psychiatric care beds in hospitals

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	398
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	190	1993	2013	142	16	2986
3	0	0

3.6.14 health_hbed_psy_nr Psychiatric care beds in hospitals ,Number

Psychiatric care beds in hospitals, Number

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	398
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	192	1993	2013	150	16	3141
3	0	0

3.6.15 health_hbed_psy_p_hthab Psychiatric care beds in hospitals ,Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Psychiatric care beds in hospitals, Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	398
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	190	1993	2013	146	16	3066
3	0	0

3.6.16 health_hned_oth_hab_p Other beds in hospitals ,Inhabitants per ... Inhabitants per 1 other beds in hospitals

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	19	1993	2013	16	17	328
1	16	1993	2013	15	20	319
2	153	1993	2013	92	13	1941
3	0	0

3.6.17 health_hned_oth_nr Other beds in hospitals ,Number Other beds in hospitals , Number

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2013	18	18	368
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	179	1993	2013	136	16	2851
3	0	0

3.6.18 health_hned_oth_p_hthab Other beds in hospitals ,Per hundred thousand inhabitants Other beds in hospitals , Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2013	18	18	368
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	177	1993	2013	133	16	2796
3	0	0

3.6.19 health_md doc_hthab Medical doctors,Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Medical doctors, Per hundred thousand inhabitants. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	20	20	411
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	188	1993	2013	147	16	3084
3	0	0

3.6.20 health_mdoc_nr Medical doctors,Number

Medical doctors, Number. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2014	19	20	413
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	189	1993	2014	147	17	3242
3	0	0

3.6.21 health_mdoc_p Medical doctors,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 Medical doctor. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	20	20	411
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	188	1993	2013	147	16	3084
3	0	0

3.6.22 health_nurs_hthab Nurses and midwives,Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Nurses and midwives, Per hundred thousand inhabitants. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2013	13	14	283
1	0	0
2	177	1995	2013	107	11	2033
3	0	0

3.6.23 health_nurs_nr Nurses and midwives,Number

Nurses and midwives, Number. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2014	13	14	285
1	0	0
2	178	1993	2014	98	12	2153
3	0	0

3.6.24 health_nurs_p Nurses and midwives,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 Nurse and midwife. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2013	13	14	283
1	0	0
2	177	1995	2013	107	11	2033
3	0	0

3.6.25 health_pharm_hthab Pharmacists,Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Pharmacists, Per hundred thousand inhabitants. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	389
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	172	1993	2013	127	16	2675
3	0	0

3.6.26 health_pharm_nr Pharmacists,Number

Pharmacists, Number. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2014	18	19	392
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	173	1993	2014	130	17	2862
3	0	0

3.6.27 health_pharm_p Pharmacists,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 Pharmacist. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1993	2013	19	19	389
1	16	1993	2013	16	21	336
2	172	1993	2013	127	16	2675
3	0	0

3.6.28 health_phys_hthab Physiotherapists ,Per hundred thousand inhabitants

Physiotherapists, Per hundred thousand inhabitants. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2013	15	16	323
1	0	0
2	168	1993	2013	89	11	1861
3	0	0

3.6.29 health_phys_nr Physiotherapists ,Number

Physiotherapists, Number. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2014	15	16	325
1	0	0
2	169	1993	2014	90	12	1975
3	0	0

3.6.30 health_phys_p Physiotherapists ,Inhabitants per ...

Inhabitants per 1 Physiotherapist. Data on physicians should refer to those "immediately serving patients", i.e. physicians who have direct contact with patients as consumers of health care services. In the context of comparing health care services across Member States, Eurostat considers that this is the concept which best describes the availability of health care resources. However, Member States use different concepts when they report the number of health care professionals. Therefore, for some countries, the data might include physicians who work in their profession but do not see patients (i.e. they work in research, administration etc.) or refer to physicians "licensed to practice" (i.e. successfully graduated physicians irrespective whether they see patients or not).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1993	2013	15	16	323
1	0	0
2	168	1993	2013	89	11	1861
3	0	0

3.7 Eurostat: Information Society Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-16)

Eurostat: Information Society Statistics Information society statistics - households and individuals. Statistics within this domain are reassessed on an annual basis in order to meet user needs and reflect the rapid pace of technological change. This approach is replicated in Eurostat's survey on ICT usage in households and by individuals. This annual survey is used to benchmark ICT-driven developments, both by following developments for core variables over time and by looking in greater depth at other aspects at a specific point in time. While the survey initially concentrated on access and connectivity issues, its scope has subsequently been extended to cover a variety of subjects (for example, e-government and e-commerce) and socioeconomic analysis (such as regional diversity,

gender specificity, differences in age, education and employment situation). The scope of the survey with respect to different technologies is also adapted so as to cover new product groups and means of delivering communication technologies to end-users.

3.7.1 is_b3_12 Last online purchase: between 3 and 12 months ago

Last online purchase: between 3 and 12 months ago

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.2 is_bfeu Ordered goods or services over the Internet from other EU countries, last 12 mon

Individuals who ordered goods or services over the Internet from sellers from other EU countries in the last 12 months

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2015	28	8	223
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.3 is_bhols Booked travel and holiday accommodation over the Internet, last 12 months

Individuals who booked travel and holiday accommodation over the Internet in the last 12 months

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	278
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.4 is_blt12 Last online purchase: in the 12 months

Last online purchase: in the 12 months

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	100	2006	2015	84	8	842
2	202	2006	2015	141	7	1407
3	0	0

3.7.5 is_bumt12 Last online purchase: more than a year ago

Last online purchase: more than a year ago

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.6 is_bumt12x Ordered goods or services over the Internet, more than a year ago or never

Individuals who ordered goods or services, over the Internet, for private use, more than a year ago or have never ordered

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.7 is_buy3 Last online purchase: in the last 3 months

Last online purchase: in the last 3 months

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.8 is_cux Computer use: Never

Persons who have never used a computer (at home, at work or any other place). % of individuals aged 16 to 74.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	278
1	100	2006	2015	82	8	817
2	218	2006	2015	136	6	1357
3	0	0

3.7.9 is_h_iacc Households with access to the internet at home (% of households)

Percentage of households with at least one member aged 16 to 74 with access to the internet at home. The access of households to internet is measured as percentage of households where any member of the household has the possibility to access the internet from home.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	100	2006	2015	85	9	852
2	202	2006	2015	140	7	1402
3	0	0

3.7.10 is_iday Frequency of internet access: daily

Individuals who used the internet with daily frequency.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.11 is_ilt12 Last internet use: in the last 12 months

Individuals used the internet in last time 12 months

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	278
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.12 is_iu3 Last internet use: in last 3 months

Individuals used the internet in last 3 months

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.13 is_iubk Internet use: internet banking

Individuals using the internet for internet banking - % of individuals aged 16 to 74. Within the last 3 months before the survey. The internet banking includes electronic transactions with a bank for payment etc. or for looking up account information.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	278
1	99	2011	2015	94	5	471
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.14 is_iucpp Internet use: civic or political participation

Internet use: civic or political participation

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2013	2015	19	2	56
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.7.15 is_iuse Frequency of internet access: once a week (including every day)

Individuals who used the internet with once a week (including every day) frequency.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	100	2006	2015	85	8	848
2	202	2006	2015	141	7	1413
3	0	0

3.7.16 is_iusell Internet use: selling goods or services

Internet use: selling goods or services

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	27	10	270
1	99	2011	2015	96	5	482
2	198	2011	2015	153	4	763
3	0	0

3.7.17 is_iusnet Internet use: participating in social networks

Internet use: participating in social networks (creating user profile, posting messages or other contributions to facebook, twitter, etc.)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2011	2015	22	4	112
1	99	2011	2015	77	4	386
2	198	2011	2015	125	3	624
3	0	0

3.7.18 is_iux Internet use: never

Individuals who have never used the internet.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	279
1	99	2008	2015	93	8	743
2	199	2008	2015	144	6	1148
3	0	0

3.7.19 is_pc_hh Households with broadband access (% of households)

Percentage of households with at least one member aged 16 to 74 that have broadband access. The availability of broadband is measured by the percentage of households that are connectable to an exchange that has been converted to support xDSL-technology, to a cable network upgraded for internet traffic, or to other broadband technologies.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	277
1	100	2006	2015	83	8	826
2	202	2006	2015	136	7	1357
3	0	0

3.7.20 is_pc_hh_iacc Households with broadband access (% of households with Internet access)

Percentage of households with at least one member aged 16 to 74 with Internet access at home that have broadband access. The internet connection used is a broadband connection (ADSL, SHDSL, cable, UMTS, etc).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2006	2015	28	10	277
1	100	2006	2015	83	8	826
2	202	2006	2015	136	7	1364
3	0	0

3.8 Eurostat: Poverty and Social Exclusion Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-16)

Eurostat: Poverty and Social Exclusion Statistics The data used in this section are primarily derived from data from EU statistics on income and living conditions (EU-SILC). The reference population is all private households and their current members residing in the territory of an EU Member State at the time of data collection; persons living in collective households and in institutions are generally excluded from the target population. The EU-28 aggregate is a population-weighted average of individual national figures.

3.8.1 pov_mat_dep_r Severe material deprivation rate

Severely materially deprived persons have living conditions severely constrained by a lack of resources, they experience at least 4 out of 9 following deprivations items: they cannot afford i) to pay rent or utility bills, ii) keep home adequately warm, iii) face unexpected expenses, iv) eat meat, fish or a protein equivalent every second day, v) a week holiday away from home, vi) a car, vii) a washing machine, viii) a colour TV, ix) a telephone. Percentage of total population.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2003	2015	23	10	293
1	43	2003	2015	27	8	346
2	89	2003	2015	64	9	837
3	0	0

3.8.2 pov_pop_lwoin People living in households with very low work intensity

People living in households with very low work intensity are people aged 0-59 living in households where the adults work less than 20% of their total work potential during the past year. Percentage of total population.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2003	2015	23	10	293
1	43	2003	2015	27	8	354
2	89	2003	2015	64	9	837
3	0	0

3.8.3 pov_pop_povr_excl People at risk of poverty or social exclusion

Persons who are at risk of poverty or severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. Persons are only counted once even if they are present in several sub-indicators. Percentage of total population.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2003	2015	23	10	293
1	43	2003	2015	27	8	346
2	89	2003	2015	64	9	837
3	0	0

3.8.4 pov_risk_pov_r At-risk-of-poverty rate (% of population)

The persons with an equivalised disposable income below the risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income. Percentage of total population.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2003	2015	23	10	293
1	43	2003	2015	27	8	346
2	89	2003	2015	64	9	837
3	0	0

3.8.5 regcode NUTS

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0
1
2
3

3.8.6 region_name name

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0
1
2
3

3.8.7 sctech_a_b_f Employment in Agriculture, forestry and fishing; mining and quarrying,Female,% o

Percentage of total employment in Agriculture, forestry and fishing; mining and quarrying,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	2008	2014	27	7	189
1	89	2008	2014	86	7	600
2	219	2008	2014	183	6	1282
3	0	0

3.8.8 sctech_a_b_m Employment in Agriculture, forestry and fishing; mining and quarrying,Male,% of

Percentage of total employment in Agriculture, forestry and fishing; mining and quarrying,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	92	7	645
2	258	2008	2014	245	7	1712
3	0	0

3.8.9 sctech_a_b_t Employment in Agriculture, forestry and fishing; mining and quarrying,Total,% of

Percentage of total employment in Agriculture, forestry and fishing; mining and quarrying,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	93	7	648
2	262	2008	2014	252	7	1767
3	0	0

3.8.10 sctech_c_f Employment in Manufacturing,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Manufacturing,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	261	2008	2014	253	7	1774
3	0	0

3.8.11 sctech_c_htc_f Employment in High-technology manufacturing,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in High-technology manufacturing,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	2008	2014	25	7	176
1	82	2008	2014	73	6	508
2	136	2008	2014	101	5	710
3	0	0

3.8.12 sctech_c_htc_m Employment in High-technology manufacturing,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in High-technology manufacturing,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	2008	2014	25	7	176
1	84	2008	2014	80	7	559
2	178	2008	2014	148	6	1036
3	0	0

3.8.13 sctech_c_htc_m_f Employment in Medium high-technology manufacturing,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Medium high-technology manufacturing,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	27	7	186
1	88	2008	2014	85	7	593
2	212	2008	2014	182	6	1273
3	0	0

3.8.14 sctech_c_htc_m_m Employment in Medium high-technology manufacturing,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Medium high-technology manufacturing,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	93	7	654
2	253	2008	2014	244	7	1709
3	0	0

3.8.15 sctech_c_htc_m_t Employment in Medium high-technology manufacturing,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Medium high-technology manufacturing,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	94	7	655
2	256	2008	2014	247	7	1732
3	0	0

3.8.16 sctech_c_htc_mh_f Employment in High and medium high-technology manufacturing,Female,% of tot emp-

Percentage of total employment in High and medium high-technology manufacturing,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	194
1	92	2008	2014	90	7	631
2	228	2008	2014	211	6	1477
3	0	0

3.8.17 sctech_c_htc_mh_m Employment in High and medium high-technology manufacturing,Male,% of tot emp-nt

Percentage of total employment in High and medium high-technology manufacturing,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	94	7	655
2	257	2008	2014	247	7	1731
3	0	0

3.8.18 sctech_c_htc_mh_t Employment in High and medium high-technology manufacturing,Total,% of tot emp-n

Percentage of total employment in High and medium high-technology manufacturing,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	94	7	656
2	257	2008	2014	250	7	1749
3	0	0

3.8.19 sctech_c_htc_t Employment in High-technology manufacturing,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in High-technology manufacturing,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	2008	2014	26	7	185
1	89	2008	2014	86	7	604
2	207	2008	2014	183	6	1280
3	0	0

3.8.20 sctech_c_ltc_f Employment in Low-technology manufacturing,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Low-technology manufacturing,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	657
2	254	2008	2014	243	7	1704
3	0	0

3.8.21 sctech_c_ltc_lm_f Employment in Low and medium low-technology manufacturing,Female,% of tot emp-nt

Percentage of total employment in Low and medium low-technology manufacturing,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	259	2008	2014	250	7	1749
3	0	0

3.8.22 sctech_c_ltc_lm_m Employment in Low and medium low-technology manufacturing,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Low and medium low-technology manufacturing,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	96	2008	2014	95	7	663
2	265	2008	2014	259	7	1810
3	0	0

3.8.23 sctech_c_ltc_lm_t Employment in Low and medium low-technology manufacturing,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Low and medium low-technology manufacturing,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	671
2	267	2008	2014	260	7	1822
3	0	0

3.8.24 sctech_c_ltc_m Employment in Low-technology manufacturing, Male, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Low-technology manufacturing, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	96	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	264	2008	2014	257	7	1797
3	0	0

3.8.25 sctech_c_ltc_m_f Employment in Medium low-technology manufacturing, Female, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Medium low-technology manufacturing, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	88	2008	2014	86	7	601
2	209	2008	2014	176	6	1230
3	0	0

3.8.26 sctech_c_ltc_m_m Employment in Medium low-technology manufacturing, Male, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Medium low-technology manufacturing, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	264	2008	2014	256	7	1789
3	0	0

3.8.27 sctech_c_ltc_m_t Employment in Medium low-technology manufacturing, Total, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Medium low-technology manufacturing, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	264	2008	2014	256	7	1794
3	0	0

3.8.28 sctech_c_ltc_t Employment in Low-technology manufacturing, Total, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Low-technology manufacturing, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	670
2	266	2008	2014	259	7	1816
3	0	0

3.8.29 sctech_c_m Employment in Manufacturing, Male, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Manufacturing, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	96	2008	2014	95	7	663
2	266	2008	2014	259	7	1812
3	0	0

3.8.30 sctech_c_t Employment in Manufacturing, Total, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Manufacturing, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	671
2	268	2008	2014	260	7	1823
3	0	0

3.8.31 sctech_d_f_f Employment in Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning sup-ply; water supply

Percentage of total employment in Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply; water supply and construction, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	93	2008	2014	92	7	645
2	239	2008	2014	215	6	1508
3	0	0

3.8.32 sctech_d_f_m Employment in Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning sup-ply; water supply

Percentage of total employment in Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply; water supply and construction, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	263	7	1842
3	0	0

3.8.33 sctech_d_f_t Employment in Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning sup-ply; water supply

Percentage of total employment in Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply; water supply and construction, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	263	7	1844
3	0	0

3.8.34 sctech_eur_habbes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector,Euro per inh.

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector,Euro per inhabitant. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	24	21	596
1	98	1990	2014	62	16	1550
2	243	1990	2014	132	14	3296
3	0	0

3.8.35 sctech_eur_habgov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sec-tor,Euro per inh.

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector,Euro per inhabitant. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	24	22	603
1	98	1990	2014	66	17	1643
2	249	1990	2014	138	14	3446
3	0	0

3.8.36 sctech_eur_habhes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector,Euro per inh.

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector,Euro per inhabitant. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	24	22	602
1	98	1990	2014	63	16	1579
2	245	1990	2014	135	14	3370
3	0	0

3.8.37 sctech_eur_habpnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector,Euro per inh.

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector,Euro per inhabitant. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2014	18	16	438
1	73	1990	2014	30	10	748
2	162	1990	2014	56	9	1395
3	0	0

3.8.38 sctech_eur_habtotal Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,Euro per inh.

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,Euro per inhabitant. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	23	20	569
1	96	1990	2014	54	14	1362
2	247	1990	2014	124	13	3101
3	0	0

3.8.39 sctech_g_i_t_f Employment in Wholesale and retail trade; accomodation and food service activiti

Percentage of total employment in Wholesale and retail trade; accomodation and food service activ-ities; activities of households as employers, Females.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	263	7	1844
3	0	0

3.8.40 sctech_g_i_t_m Employment in Wholesale and retail trade; accomodation and food service activiti

Percentage of total employment in Wholesale and retail trade; accomodation and food service activ-ities; activities of households as employers, Males.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	263	7	1844
3	0	0

3.8.41 sctech_g_i_t_t Employment in Wholesale and retail trade; accomodation and food service activiti

Percentage of total employment in Wholesale and retail trade; accomodation and food service activ-ities; activities of households as employers, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	678
2	271	2008	2014	264	7	1850
3	0	0

3.8.42 sctech_g_u_f Employment in Services,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Services,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.43 sctech_g_u_m Employment in Services,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Services,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.44 sctech_g_u_t Employment in Services,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Services,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.45 sctech_h52_n79_f Employment in Land transport, transport via pipelines, wa-ter transport, air tran

Percentage of total employment in Land transport, transport via pipelines, water transport, air trans-port, warehousing and support activities for transportation; travel agency, tour operator reservation services and related activities, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	93	2008	2014	92	7	647
2	220	2008	2014	196	6	1374
3	0	0

3.8.46 sctech_h52_n79_m Employment in Land transport, transport via pipelines, water transport, air tran

Percentage of total employment in Land transport, transport via pipelines, water transport, air transport, warehousing and support activities for transportation; travel agency, tour operator reservation services and related activities, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	265	2008	2014	258	7	1809
3	0	0

3.8.47 sctech_h52_n79_t Employment in Land transport, transport via pipelines, wa-ter transport, air tran

Percentage of total employment in Land transport, transport via pipelines, water transport, air transport, warehousing and support activities for transportation; travel agency, tour operator reservation services and related activities, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	95	7	667
2	268	2008	2014	261	7	1825
3	0	0

3.8.48 sctech_hrst_pc_act HR in science and tech. with tert.educ(ISCED) in science and tech,% active pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology as a share of the active population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the active population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	96	16	1540
2	268	1999	2014	257	15	4111
3	0	0

3.8.49 sctech_hrst_pc_pop HR in science and tech.with tert.educ(ISCED)and/or in science and tech,% tot pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology as a share of the total population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the total population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	96	16	1540
2	268	1999	2014	257	15	4111
3	0	0

3.8.50 sctech_hrstc_pc_act HR in science and tech.with tert.educ(ISCED)and in sci-ence and tech,% active pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) with tertiary education (ISCED) and employed in science and technology as a share of the active population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the active population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	95	16	1521
2	268	1999	2014	255	15	4072
3	0	0

3.8.51 sctech_hrstc_pc_pop HR in science and tech.with tertiary educ(ISCED)in sci-ence and tech,% tot pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) with tertiary education (ISCED) and employed in science and technology as a share of the total population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the total population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	95	16	1521
2	268	1999	2014	255	15	4072
3	0	0

3.8.52 sctech_hrste_pc_act HR in science and tech.Persons with tertiary educ(ISCED),% of active pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) with tertiary education (ISCED) as a share of the active population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the active

population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	96	16	1533
2	268	1999	2014	256	15	4103
3	0	0

3.8.53 sctech_hrste_pc_pop HR in science and tech. Persons with tertiary educ(ISCED),% of tot pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) with tertiary education (ISCED) as a share of the total population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the total population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	96	16	1533
2	268	1999	2014	256	15	4103
3	0	0

3.8.54 sctech_hrsto_pc_act HR in science and tech. Persons employed in science and tech,% of active pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) employed in science and technology as a share of the active population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the active population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	96	16	1540
2	268	1999	2014	257	15	4105
3	0	0

3.8.55 sctech_hrsto_pc_pop HR in science and tech. Persons employed in science and tech,% of tot pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST) employed in science and technology as a share of the total population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the total population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	97	1999	2014	96	16	1540
2	268	1999	2014	257	15	4105
3	0	0

3.8.56 sctech_htc_f Employment in High-technology sectors (high-technology manufacturing and knowledge-intensive high-technology services), Female.

Percentage of total employment in High-technology sectors (high-technology manufacturing and knowledge-intensive high-technology services), Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	92	2008	2014	91	7	634
2	220	2008	2014	199	6	1390
3	0	0

3.8.57 sctech_htc_m Employment in High-technology sectors (high-technology manufacturing and knowledge-intensive high-technology services), Male.

Percentage of total employment in High-technology sectors (high-technology manufacturing and knowledge-intensive high-technology services), Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	252	2008	2014	234	6	1636
3	0	0

3.8.58 sctech_htc_t Employment in High-technology sectors (high-technology manufacturing and knowledge-intensive high-technology services), Total.

Percentage of total employment in High-technology sectors (high-technology manufacturing and knowledge-intensive high-technology services), Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	258	2008	2014	248	7	1733
3	0	0

3.8.59 sctech_j_f Employment in Information and communication, Female, % of total employment.

Percentage of total employment in Information and communication, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	91	2008	2014	88	7	616
2	192	2008	2014	166	6	1160
3	0	0

3.8.60 sctech_j_m Employment in Information and communication, Male, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Information and communication, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	656
2	237	2008	2014	218	6	1523
3	0	0

3.11.5 sctech_j_t Employment in Information and communication, Total, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Information and communication, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	256	2008	2014	240	7	1679
3	0	0

3.8.62 sctech_k_f Employment in Financial and insurance activities, Female, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Financial and insurance activities, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	93	7	652
2	245	2008	2014	230	7	1608
3	0	0

3.8.63 sctech_k_l_f Employment in Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, Female,

Percentage of total employment in Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, Female,

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	93	7	654
2	254	2008	2014	240	7	1677
3	0	0

3.8.64 sctech_k_l_m Employment in Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, Male, %

Percentage of total employment in Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	94	2008	2014	93	7	648
2	239	2008	2014	224	7	1569
3	0	0

3.8.65 sctech_k_l_t Employment in Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, Total, %

Percentage of total employment in Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	264	2008	2014	255	7	1786
3	0	0

3.8.66 sctech_k_m Employment in Financial and insurance activities, Male, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Financial and insurance activities, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	27	7	191
1	93	2008	2014	91	7	636
2	227	2008	2014	206	6	1445
3	0	0

3.8.67 sctech_k_t Employment in Financial and insurance activities, Total, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Financial and insurance activities, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	259	2008	2014	249	7	1743
3	0	0

3.8.68 sctech_kis_f Employment in Total knowledge-intensive services, Female, % of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Total knowledge-intensive services, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.69 sctech_kis_htc_f Employment in Knowledge-intensive high-technology services,Female,% of tot emp-n

Percentage of total employment in Knowledge-intensive high-technology services,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	90	2008	2014	86	7	604
2	186	2008	2014	159	6	1111
3	0	0

3.8.70 sctech_kis_htc_m Employment in Knowledge-intensive high-technology ser-vices,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Knowledge-intensive high-technology services,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	93	7	654
2	238	2008	2014	214	6	1499
3	0	0

3.8.71 sctech_kis_htc_t Employment in Knowledge-intensive high-technology services,Total,% of tot emp-nt

Percentage of total employment in Knowledge-intensive high-technology services,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	253	2008	2014	236	7	1649
3	0	0

3.8.72 sctech_kis_m Employment in Total knowledge-intensive services,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Total knowledge-intensive services,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.73 sctech_kis_mkt_oth_f Employment in Knowledge-intensive market services (except financial intermediati

Percentage of total employment in Knowledge-intensive market services (except financial intermediation and high-technology services), Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	260	2008	2014	245	7	1716
3	0	0

3.8.74 sctech_kis_mkt_oth_m Employment in Knowledge-intensive market services (except financial intermediati

Percentage of total employment in Knowledge-intensive market services (except financial intermediation and high-technology services), Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	265	2008	2014	256	7	1793
3	0	0

3.8.75 sctech_kis_mkt_oth_t Employment in Knowledge-intensive market services (except financial intermediati

Percentage of total employment in Knowledge-intensive market services (except financial intermediation and high-technology services), Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	96	2008	2014	95	7	662
2	269	2008	2014	260	7	1822
3	0	0

3.8.76 sctech_kis_oth_f Employment in Other knowledge-intensive services,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other knowledge-intensive services,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.77 sctech_kis_oth_m Employment in Other knowledge-intensive services,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other knowledge-intensive services,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	264	7	1845
3	0	0

3.8.78 sctech_kis_oth_t Employment in Other knowledge-intensive services,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other knowledge-intensive services,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.79 sctech_kis_t Employment in Total knowledge-intensive services,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Total knowledge-intensive services,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.80 sctech_lkis_f Employment in Total less knowledge-intensive services ,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Total less knowledge-intensive services ,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	96	7	674
2	271	2008	2014	264	7	1846
3	0	0

3.8.81 sctech_lkis_m Employment in Total less knowledge-intensive services ,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Total less knowledge-intensive services ,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	677
2	271	2008	2014	264	7	1849
3	0	0

3.8.82 sctech_ikis_mkt_f Employment in Less knowledge-intensive market services,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Less knowledge-intensive market services,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	264	7	1845
3	0	0

3.8.83 sctech_ikis_mkt_m Employment in Less knowledge-intensive market services,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Less knowledge-intensive market services,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	96	7	674
2	271	2008	2014	264	7	1846
3	0	0

3.8.84 sctech_ikis_mkt_t Employment in Less knowledge-intensive market services,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Less knowledge-intensive market services,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.85 sctech_ikis_oth_f Employment in Other less knowledge-intensive services,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other less knowledge-intensive services,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	260	2008	2014	248	7	1735
3	0	0

3.8.86 sctech_ikis_oth_m Employment in Other less knowledge-intensive services,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other less knowledge-intensive services,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	657
2	245	2008	2014	222	6	1557
3	0	0

3.8.87 sctech_ikis_oth_t Employment in Other less knowledge-intensive services,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other less knowledge-intensive services,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	266	2008	2014	257	7	1802
3	0	0

3.8.88 sctech_ikis_t Employment in Total less knowledge-intensive services ,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Total less knowledge-intensive services ,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.89 sctech_m_f Employment in Professional, scientific and technical activities,Female,% of tot

Percentage of total employment in Professional, scientific and technical activities,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	257	2008	2014	240	7	1681
3	0	0

3.8.90 sctech_m_m Employment in Professional, scientific and technical activities,Male,% of tot em

Percentage of total employment in Professional, scientific and technical activities,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	254	2008	2014	241	7	1688
3	0	0

3.8.91 sctech_m_t Employment in Professional, scientific and technical activities, Total, % of tot e

Percentage of total employment in Professional, scientific and technical activities, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	265	2008	2014	258	7	1809
3	0	0

3.8.92 sctech_mio_eurbes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million euro

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million euro. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	19	1990	2014	13	17	315
1	88	1990	2014	43	12	1070
2	248	1990	2014	125	13	3132
3	0	0

3.8.93 sctech_mio_eurgov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million euro

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million euro. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	1990	2014	19	20	471
1	106	1990	2014	66	16	1647
2	269	1990	2014	144	13	3601
3	0	0

3.8.94 sctech_mio_eurhes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million euro

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million euro. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	22	1990	2014	15	17	378
1	106	1990	2014	59	14	1470
2	266	1990	2014	141	13	3517
3	0	0

3.8.95 sctech_mio_eurpnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector,Million euro

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector,Million euro. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2014	18	16	439
1	82	1990	2014	33	10	814
2	181	1990	2014	60	8	1498
3	0	0

3.8.96 sctech_mio_eurtotal Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,Million euro

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,Million euro. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	17	1990	2014	11	16	274
1	79	1990	2014	35	11	866
2	243	1990	2014	112	12	2804
3	0	0

3.8.97 sctech_mio_nacbes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector,Million units of

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million units of national currency. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	16	1990	2014	10	16	253
1	81	1990	2014	41	13	1021
2	234	1990	2014	117	12	2921
3	0	0

3.8.98 sctech_mio_nacgov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector,Million units of nat.cur

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million units of national currency. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1990	2014	14	18	362
1	97	1990	2014	62	16	1539
2	263	1990	2014	139	13	3480
3	0	0

3.8.99 sctech_mio_naches Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million units of nat

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million units of national currency. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1990	2014	13	16	314
1	100	1990	2014	56	14	1403
2	253	1990	2014	133	13	3332
3	0	0

3.8.100 sctech_mio_nacnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Million units of n

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Million units of national currency. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2014	18	16	439
1	82	1990	2014	33	10	814
2	181	1990	2014	60	8	1498
3	0	0

3.8.101 sctech_mio_nactotal Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Million units of nat.cur

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Million units of national currency. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	14	1990	2014	9	16	222
1	74	1990	2014	31	10	773
2	221	1990	2014	102	12	2559
3	0	0

3.8.102 sctech_mio_pps_kp05bes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million PPS2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) at 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	17	1995	2014	13	15	258
1	82	1990	2014	38	12	953
2	249	1990	2014	118	12	2962
3	0	0

3.8.103 sctech_mio_pps_kp05gov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million PPS2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) at 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	22	1990	2014	16	18	394
1	103	1991	2014	65	15	1548
2	268	1991	2014	141	13	3389
3	0	0

3.8.104 sctech_mio_pps_kp05hes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million PPS2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) at 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	20	1990	2014	13	16	325
1	104	1991	2014	59	14	1406
2	265	1991	2014	141	13	3381
3	0	0

3.8.105 sctech_mio_pps_kp05pnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Million PPS2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Million Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) at 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1990	2014	16	15	400
1	81	1992	2014	33	9	748
2	180	1992	2014	62	8	1425
3	0	0

3.8.106 sctech_mio_pps_kp05total Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Million PPS2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Million Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) at 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	15	1995	2014	10	13	196
1	72	1991	2014	32	11	761
2	242	1991	2014	112	11	2679
3	0	0

3.8.107 sctech_mio_ppsbes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million PPS

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Million PPS (purchasing power standard). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	17	1995	2014	13	15	262
1	87	1995	2014	48	11	953
2	252	1995	2014	143	11	2854
3	0	0

3.8.108 sctech_mio_ppsgov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million PPS

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Million PPS (purchasing power standard). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	24	1995	2014	20	17	398
1	105	1995	2014	74	14	1486
2	268	1995	2014	164	12	3284
3	0	0

3.8.109 sctech_mio_ppshes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million PPS

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Million PPS (purchasing power standard). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1995	2014	16	15	322
1	106	1995	2014	67	13	1344
2	265	1995	2014	164	12	3280
3	0	0

3.8.110 sctech_mio_ppspnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Million PPS

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Million PPS (purchasing power standard). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1995	2014	19	15	388
1	81	1995	2014	37	9	744
2	180	1995	2014	71	8	1419
3	0	0

3.8.111 sctech_mio_ppstotal Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,Million PPS

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Million PPS (purchasing power standard). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	15	1995	2014	10	13	198
1	71	1995	2014	37	10	735
2	242	1995	2014	129	11	2589
3	0	0

3.8.112 sctech_n_f Employment in Administrative and support service activities,Female,% of tot emp-

Percentage of total employment in Administrative and support service activities,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	655
2	246	2008	2014	230	7	1609
3	0	0

3.8.113 sctech_n_m Employment in Administrative and support service activities,Male,% of tot emp-
nt

Percentage of total employment in Administrative and support service activities,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	255	2008	2014	242	7	1696
3	0	0

3.8.114 sctech_n_t Employment in Administrative and support service activities,Total,% of tot emp-
n

Percentage of total employment in Administrative and support service activities,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	96	2008	2014	95	7	662
2	268	2008	2014	259	7	1812
3	0	0

3.8.115 sctech_o_u_f Employment in Public administration; activities of extraterritorial
organisation

Percentage of total employment in Public administration; activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	95	7	667
2	270	2008	2014	262	7	1836
3	0	0

3.8.116 sctech_o_u_m Employment in Public administration; activities of extraterritorial organisation

Percentage of total employment in Public administration; activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	269	2008	2014	263	7	1839
3	0	0

3.8.117 sctech_o_u_t Employment in Public administration; activities of extraterritorial organisation

Percentage of total employment in Public administration; activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	264	7	1845
3	0	0

3.8.118 sctech_p_f Employment in Education,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Education,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	269	2008	2014	262	7	1837
3	0	0

3.8.119 sctech_p_m Employment in Education,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Education,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	658
2	262	2008	2014	253	7	1771
3	0	0

3.8.120 sctech_p_t Employment in Education,Total,% of tot emp-nt,
Percentage of total employment in Education,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	97	2008	2014	96	7	673
2	270	2008	2014	263	7	1840
3	0	0

3.8.121 sctech_pc_gdpbes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector,% of GDP

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	21	19	537
1	98	2000	2014	73	11	1098
2	258	2000	2014	175	10	2619
3	0	0

3.8.122 sctech_pc_gdpgov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sec-tor,% of GDP

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	22	19	539
1	98	2000	2014	76	12	1140
2	257	2000	2014	177	10	2652
3	0	0

3.8.123 sctech_pc_gdphes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector,% of GDP

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	22	19	538
1	98	2000	2014	76	12	1145
2	254	2000	2014	178	11	2673
3	0	0

3.8.124 sctech_pc_gdppnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector,% of GDP

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1990	2014	16	15	402
1	70	2000	2014	37	8	559
2	170	2000	2014	83	7	1240
3	0	0

3.8.125 sctech_pc_gdptotal Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,% of GDP

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP). Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	22	19	545
1	98	2000	2014	69	11	1040
2	266	2000	2014	178	10	2664
3	0	0

3.8.126 sctech_pps_hab_kp05bes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector,PPS per inh. 2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Business enterprise sector, Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) per inhabitant at constant 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	21	19	533
1	98	1990	2014	59	15	1481
2	244	1990	2014	126	13	3139
3	0	0

3.8.127 sctech_pps_hab_kp05gov Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector,PPS per inh. 2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Government sector, Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) per inhabitant at constant 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	21	19	535
1	98	1991	2014	65	16	1554
2	249	1991	2014	136	13	3266
3	0	0

3.8.128 sctech_pps_hab_kp05hes Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector,PPS per inh. 2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Higher education sector, Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) per inhabitant at constant 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	21	19	534
1	98	1991	2014	63	15	1505
2	245	1991	2014	135	13	3248
3	0	0

3.8.129 sctech_pps_hab_kp05pnp Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector,PPS per inh. 2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in Private non-profit sector, Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) per inhabitant at constant 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1990	2014	16	15	399
1	73	1992	2014	30	9	690
2	162	1992	2014	58	8	1333
3	0	0

3.8.130 sctech_pps_hab_kp05total Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors,PPS per inh. 2005

Total intramural R&D expenditure in All sectors, Purchasing Power Standard (PPS) per inhabitant at constant 2005 prices. Intramural R&D expenditures are all expenditures for R&D performed within a statistical unit or sector of the economy during a specific period, whatever the source of funds.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	21	19	530
1	96	1991	2014	55	14	1317
2	246	1991	2014	126	12	3022
3	0	0

3.8.131 sctech_q_f Employment in Human health and social work activities,Female,% of total employment,

Percentage of total employment in Human health and social work activities,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	679
2	271	2008	2014	264	7	1849
3	0	0

3.8.132 sctech_q_m Employment in Human health and social work activities, Male, % of total employment,

Percentage of total employment in Human health and social work activities, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	261	2008	2014	247	7	1730
3	0	0

3.8.133 sctech_q_t Employment in Human health and social work activities, Total, % of total employment,

Percentage of total employment in Human health and social work activities, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.134 sctech_r_f Employment in Arts, entertainment and recreation, Female, % of total employment,

Percentage of total employment in Arts, entertainment and recreation, Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	92	2008	2014	88	7	617
2	207	2008	2014	175	6	1226
3	0	0

3.8.135 sctech_r_m Employment in Arts, entertainment and recreation, Male, % of total employment,

Percentage of total employment in Arts, entertainment and recreation, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	90	2008	2014	88	7	614
2	209	2008	2014	175	6	1228
3	0	0

3.8.136 sctech_r_t Employment in Arts, entertainment and recreation,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Arts, entertainment and recreation,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	93	7	653
2	255	2008	2014	232	6	1623
3	0	0

3.8.137 sctech_rse_fte_f Researchers in all sectors,Full-time equivalent,Females

Researchers in all sectors, Full-time equivalent (FTE), Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	3	1998	2013	2	10	30
1	23	1998	2013	8	5	126
2	118	1998	2013	54	7	862
3	0	0

3.8.138 sctech_rse_fte_t Researchers in all sectors,Full-time equivalent,Total

Researchers in all sectors, Full-time equivalent (FTE), Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	2	1991	2014	1	16	32
1	16	1991	2014	5	8	120
2	88	1991	2014	25	7	604
3	0	0

3.8.139 sctech_rse_hc_f Researchers in all sectors,Head count,Females

Researchers in all sectors, Head count, Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the con-ception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	3	1998	2013	2	11	32
1	13	1998	2013	6	8	98
2	109	1998	2013	45	7	714
3	0	0

3.8.140 sctech_rse_hc_t Researchers in all sectors,Head count,Total

Researchers in all sectors, Head count, Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	2	1998	2009	1	5	10
1	12	1998	2013	6	8	90
2	48	1998	2013	19	6	307
3	0	0

3.8.141 sctech_rse_papfte_f Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,% of active pop - in FTE,Fem

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE),Female. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1996	2013	16	11	291
1	56	1998	2013	33	9	525
2	158	1998	2013	83	8	1325
3	0	0

3.8.142 sctech_rse_papfte_t Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,% of active pop - in FTE,Tot

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Total. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2014	22	18	501
1	98	1998	2014	59	10	1004
2	266	1998	2014	147	9	2505
3	0	0

3.8.143 sctech_rse_paphc_f Researchers in all sectors,% of active pop - in HC,Females

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in head count (HC), Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1996	2013	19	12	339
1	68	1998	2013	37	9	587
2	195	1998	2013	93	8	1495
3	0	0

3.8.144 sctech_rse_paphc_t Researchers in all sectors,% of active pop - in HC,Total

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in head count (HC), Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2013	18	14	386
1	98	1998	2013	53	9	853
2	266	1998	2013	134	8	2139
3	0	0

3.8.145 sctech_rse_ptefte_f Researchers in all sectors,% of total emp. - in FTE,Females

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1996	2013	16	11	291
1	56	1998	2013	33	9	527
2	158	1998	2013	83	8	1329
3	0	0

3.8.146 sctech_rse_ptefte_t Researchers in all sectors,% of total emp. - in FTE,Total

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2014	22	18	501
1	98	1998	2014	60	10	1012
2	266	1998	2014	148	9	2513
3	0	0

3.8.147 sctech_rse_ptehc_f Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,% of total emp - in head coun

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in head count (HC),Female. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1996	2013	19	12	339
1	68	1998	2013	37	9	589
2	195	1998	2013	94	8	1501
3	0	0

3.8.148 sctech_rse_ptehc_t Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,% of total emp - in head coun

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in head count (HC), Total. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2013	18	14	386
1	98	1998	2013	54	9	857
2	266	1998	2013	134	8	2147
3	0	0

3.8.149 sctech_rtot_pmin Patent applications to the EPO, Per million inhabitants

Patent applications to the EPO, Per million inhabitants. Patents reflect a country's inventive activity. Patents also show the country's capacity to exploit knowledge and translate it into potential economic gains. In this context, indicators based on patent statistics are widely used to assess the inventive performance of countries. This domain provides users with data concerning patent applications / granted to the European Patent Office - EPO, patents granted by the United States Patent and Trademark Office - USPTO and triadic patent families. EPO data refer to all patent applications by priority year as opposed to patents granted by priority year, which is the case of USPTO data.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2012	27	23	631
1	98	1990	2012	70	16	1602
2	270	1990	2012	182	15	4177
3	1293	1990	2012	735	13	16904

3.8.150 sctech_rtot_pminapop Patent applications to the EPO, number

Patent applications to the EPO, number. Patents reflect a country's inventive activity. Patents also show the country's capacity to exploit knowledge and translate it into potential economic gains. In this context, indicators based on patent statistics are widely used to assess the inventive performance of countries. This domain provides users with data concerning patent applications / granted to the European Patent Office - EPO, patents granted by the United States Patent and Trademark Office - USPTO and triadic patent families. EPO data refer to all patent applications by priority year as opposed to patents granted by priority year, which is the case of USPTO data.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2012	28	14	387
1	98	1999	2012	96	14	1337
2	270	1999	2012	249	13	3480
3	0	0

3.8.151 sctech_s_f Employment in Other service activities,Female,% of tot emp-nt, Percentage of total employment in Other service activities,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	256	2008	2014	234	6	1639
3	0	0

3.8.152 sctech_s_m Employment in Other service activities,Male,% of tot emp-nt, Percentage of total employment in Other service activities,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	92	7	644
2	231	2008	2014	193	6	1349
3	0	0

3.8.153 sctech_s_t Employment in Other service activities,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Other service activities,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	95	2008	2014	94	7	659
2	265	2008	2014	255	7	1783
3	0	0

3.8.154 sctech_se_pc_act HRces in science and tech.Scientists and engineers,% of active pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST)-Scientists and engineers as a share of the active population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the active population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	27	16	437
1	96	1999	2014	91	15	1453
2	266	1999	2014	233	14	3724
3	0	0

3.8.155 sctech_se_pc_pop HR in science and tech.Scientists and engineers,% of tot pop

Human resources in science and technology (HRST)-Scientists and engineers as a share of the total population in the age group 15-74 at the regional NUTS 2 level. The data shows the total population in the age group 15-74 that is classified as HRST (i.e. having successfully completed an education at the third level or being employed in science and technology) as a percentage of total active population aged 15-74. HRST are measured mainly using the concepts and definitions laid down in the Canberra Manual, OECD, Paris, 1995.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	27	16	437
1	96	1999	2014	91	15	1453
2	266	1999	2014	233	14	3724
3	0	0

3.8.156 sctech_tot_f Employment in All NACE activities,Female,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in All NACE activities,Female.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.157 sctech_tot_fte_f Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,Full-time equivalent,Females

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Full-time equivalent (FTE),Females. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	3	1998	2013	2	10	29
1	5	1998	2013	2	6	31
2	6	1998	2013	2	5	32
3	0	0

3.8.158 sctech_tot_fte_t Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,Full-time equivalent,Total

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Full-time equivalent (FTE), Total. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	2	1991	2009	1	8	16
1	16	1990	2013	5	8	122
2	70	1990	2013	22	8	527
3	0	0

3.8.159 sctech_tot_hc_f Researchers in all sectors,Head count,Females

Researchers in all sectors,Head count,Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	3	1998	2013	1	7	22
1	11	1998	2013	5	8	84
2	74	1998	2013	26	6	416
3	0	0

3.8.160 sctech_tot_hc_t Researchers in all sectors,Head count,Total

Researchers in all sectors,Head count, Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	1	2003	2003	1	1	1
1	13	1990	2013	4	8	102
2	45	1990	2013	12	6	292
3	0	0

3.8.161 sctech_tot_m Employment in All NACE activities, Male, % of tot emp-nt, Percentage of total employment in All NACE activities, Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.162 sctech_tot_n Patent applications to the EPO, Per million of active population

Patent applications to the EPO, Per million of active population. Patents reflect a country's inventive activity. Patents also show the country's capacity to exploit knowledge and translate it into potential economic gains. In this context, indicators based on patent statistics are widely used to assess the inventive performance of countries. This domain provides users with data concerning patent applications / granted to the European Patent Office - EPO, patents granted by the United States Patent and Trademark Office - USPTO and triadic patent families. EPO data refer to all patent applications by priority year as opposed to patents granted by priority year, which is the case of USPTO data.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2012	27	23	632
1	124	1990	2012	112	21	2573
2	296	1990	2012	267	21	6150
3	1322	1990	2012	1110	19	25534

3.8.163 sctech_tot_papfte_f Researchers in all sectors, % of active pop - in FTE, Females

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1996	2013	16	11	285
1	15	1998	2013	8	8	125
2	10	1998	2013	5	8	79
3	0	0

3.8.164 sctech_tot_papfte_t Researchers in all sectors, % of active pop - in FTE, Total

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2014	22	18	515
1	98	1998	2014	63	11	1072
2	267	1998	2014	156	10	2647
3	0	0

3.8.165 sctech_tot_paphc_f Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,% of active pop - in HC,Femal

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in head count (HC),Female. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1996	2013	19	12	339
1	68	1998	2013	37	9	588
2	195	1998	2013	94	8	1504
3	0	0

3.8.166 sctech_tot_paphc_t Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors,% of active pop - in HC,Total

Total R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors, Percentage of active population - numerator in head count (HC), Total. R&D personnel include all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff. Those providing an indirect service, such as canteen and security staff, should be excluded.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2013	19	15	407
1	98	1998	2013	56	9	894
2	266	1998	2013	139	8	2228
3	0	0

3.8.167 sctech_tot_ptefte_f Researchers in all sectors,% of total emp. - in FTE,Females

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1996	2013	16	11	285
1	15	1998	2013	8	8	125
2	10	1998	2013	5	8	79
3	0	0

3.8.168 sctech_tot_ptefte_t Researchers in all sectors,% of total emp. - in FTE,Total

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in full-time equivalent (FTE), Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2014	22	18	515
1	98	1998	2014	64	11	1080
2	267	1998	2014	156	10	2655
3	0	0

3.8.169 sctech_tot_ptehc_f Researchers in all sectors,% of total emp - in head count HC,Females

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in head count (HC), Females. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1996	2013	19	12	339
1	68	1998	2013	37	9	590
2	195	1998	2013	94	8	1510
3	0	0

3.8.170 sctech_tot_ptehc_t Researchers in all sectors,% of total emp - in head count HC,Total

Researchers in all sectors, Percentage of total employment - numerator in head count (HC), Total. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1992	2013	19	15	407
1	98	1998	2013	56	9	898
2	266	1998	2013	140	8	2236
3	0	0

3.8.171 sctech_tot_t Employment in All NACE activities,Total,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in All NACE activities,Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	2008	2014	28	7	196
1	98	2008	2014	97	7	680
2	271	2008	2014	265	7	1852
3	0	0

3.8.172 sctech_unk_m Employment in Unknown NACE activity,Male,% of tot emp-nt,

Percentage of total employment in Unknown NACE activity,Male.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.8.173 sctech_unk_t Employment in Unknown NACE activity, Total, % of tot emp-nt, Percentage of total employment in Unknown NACE activity, Total.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.9 Eurostat: Science and Technology Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-17)

Eurostat: Science and Technology Statistics Defining high-tech in Eurostat's statistics involves three different approaches: the sector approach looks at the high-tech manufacturing sector, the medium high-tech manufacturing sector, and the high-tech knowledge-intensive service sector, focusing on employment and economic indicators; the product approach considers whether a product is high-tech or not and examines trade in high-tech products; the patent approach distinguishes high-tech patents from others and also defines biotechnology patents.

3.10 Eurostat: Tourism Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-17)

Eurostat: Tourism Statistics The statistical definition of tourism is broader than the common definition employed on an everyday basis, as it encompasses not only private trips but also business trips. This is primarily because tourism is viewed from an economic perspective, whereby private visitors on holiday and visitors making business trips have broadly similar consumption patterns (transport, accommodation and restaurant / catering services). As such, it may be of secondary interest to providers of tourism services whether their customers are private tourists on holiday or visitors on a business trip. Tourist accommodation establishments are defined according to the activity classification, NACE. They are units providing, as a paid service, short-term or short-stay accommodation services, as defined by NACE Groups 55.1-55.3: hotels and similar accommodation (NACE Group 55.1); holiday and other short-stay accommodation (NACE Group 55.2); and, camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks (NACE Group 55.3). The number of nights spent (or overnight stays) is the principal indicator used for analysis, covering each night a guest / tourist actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment. No regional statistics are available for nights spent in non-rented accommodation or for same-day visits.

3.10.1 tour_camp_rec_bpl Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of bed-places

Camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of bed-places. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. One camping pitch should equal four bed places if the actual number of bed places is not known.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	622
1	101	1990	2015	76	20	1971
2	276	1990	2015	199	19	5183
3	0	0

3.10.2 tour_camp_rec_br Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks, Bedrooms

Camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Bedrooms. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. A bedroom is the unit formed by one room or groups of rooms constituting an indivisible rental whole in an accommodation establishment or dwelling. Rooms may be single, double or multiple, depending on whether they are equipped permanently to accommodate one, two or several people (it is useful to classify the rooms respectively). The number of existing rooms is the number the establishment habitually has available to accommodate guests (overnight visitors), excluding rooms used by the employees working for the establishment. If a room is used as a permanent residence (for more than a year) it should not be included. Bathrooms and toilets do not count as a room. An apartment is a special type of room. It consists of one or more rooms and has a kitchen unit and its own bathroom and toilet. Apartments may be with hotel services (in apartment hotels) or without hotel services. Cabins, cottages, huts, chalets, bungalows and villas can be treated like bedrooms and apartments, i.e. to be let as a unit.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.3 tour_camp_rec_nr_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and traile

Total nights spent by non-residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	23	636
1	101	1990	2015	69	18	1786
2	276	1990	2015	180	17	4670
3	0	0

3.10.4 tour_camp_rec_nr_r Nights spent by residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer pa

Total nights spent by residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommo-dation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	23	633
1	101	1990	2015	70	18	1817
2	276	1990	2015	183	17	4761
3	0	0

3.10.5 tour_camp_rec_nr_tot Nights spent at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks (Number)

Total nights spent at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	625
1	101	1990	2015	68	18	1779
2	276	1990	2015	179	17	4660
3	0	0

3.10.6 tour_camp_rec_nre Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of establishments

Camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of establishments. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The local unit is an enterprise or part thereof situated in a geographically identified place. At or from this place economic activity is carried out for which - save for certain exceptions - one or more persons work (even if only part-time) for one and the same enterprise. The accommodation establishment conforms to the definition of local unit as the production unit. This is irrespective of whether the accommodation of tourists is the main or secondary activity. This means that all establishments are classified in the accommodation sector if their capacity exceeds the national minimum even if the major part of turnover may come from restaurant or other services.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	646
1	101	1990	2015	79	20	2045
2	276	1990	2015	205	19	5335
3	0	0

3.10.7 tour_camp_rec_p_km2_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and traile

Total nights spent by non-residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.8 tour_camp_rec_p_km2_r Nights spent by residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer pa

Total nights spent by residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence

of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.9 tour_camp_rec_p_km2_tot Nights spent at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks (per squa

Total nights spent at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.10 tour_camp_rec_p_thab_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and traile

Total nights spent by non-residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is

indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.11 tour_camp_rec_p_thab_r Nights spent by residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer pa

Total nights spent by residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.12 tour_camp_rec_p_thab_tot Nights spent at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks (per 1000

Total nights spent at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.13 tour_camp_rec_pc_tot_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and traile

Total nights spent by non-residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommo-dation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.14 tour_camp_rec_pc_tot_r Nights spent by residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer pa

Total nights spent by residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommo-dation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.15 tour_camp_rec_pc_tot_tot Nights spent at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer parks (% of tot

Total nights spent at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.16 tour_camp_rec_pch_pre_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and traile

Total nights spent by non-residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2015	24	23	611
1	94	1990	2015	63	17	1637
2	260	1990	2015	163	16	4243
3	0	0

3.10.17 tour_camp_rec_pch_pre_r Nights spent by residents at Camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and trailer pa

Total nights spent by residents at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return

within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2015	23	23	608
1	94	1990	2015	64	18	1672
2	262	1990	2015	167	17	4354
3	0	0

3.10.18 tour_camp_rec_pch_pre_tot Nights spent at Camping grounds, recr. vehi-cle parks and trailer parks (% change)

Total nights spent at camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2015	23	22	598
1	94	1991	2015	65	17	1625
2	261	1991	2015	170	16	4240
3	0	0

3.10.19 tour_hap_nr_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; ca

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	640
1	101	1990	2015	75	19	1940
2	276	1990	2015	192	18	4983
3	0	0

3.10.20 tour_hap_nr_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; campin

Total nights spent by residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	644
1	101	1990	2015	75	19	1958
2	276	1990	2015	193	18	5029
3	0	0

3.10.21 tour_hap_nr_tot Nights spent at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, re

Total nights spent at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	638
1	101	1990	2015	74	19	1916
2	276	1990	2015	190	18	4941
3	0	0

3.10.22 tour_hap_p_km2_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; ca

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.23 tour_hap_p_km2_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; campin

Total nights spent by residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.24 tour_hap_p_km2_tot Nights spent at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, re

Total nights spent at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	22	21	584
1	98	1990	2015	65	17	1701
2	267	1990	2015	169	16	4383
3	0	0

3.10.25 tour_hap_p_thab_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; ca

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.26 tour_hap_p_thab_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; campin

Total nights spent by residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at

the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.27 tour_hap_p_thab_tot Nights spent at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, re

Total nights spent at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2014	25	23	630
1	98	1990	2014	63	16	1582
2	269	1990	2014	163	15	4083
3	0	0

3.10.28 tour_hap_pc_tot_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; ca

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km². A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	638
1	101	1990	2015	74	19	1914
2	275	1990	2015	190	18	4938
3	0	0

3.10.29 tour_hap_pc_tot_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; campin

Total nights spent by residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	643
1	101	1990	2015	74	19	1921
2	275	1990	2015	190	18	4940
3	0	0

3.10.30 tour_hap_pc_tot_tot Nights spent at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, re

Total nights spent at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	638
1	101	1990	2015	74	19	1916
2	275	1990	2015	190	18	4940
3	0	0

3.10.31 tour_hap_pch_pre_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; ca

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	622
1	98	1990	2015	71	19	1836
2	268	1990	2015	179	17	4658
3	0	0

3.10.32 tour_hap_pch_pre_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; campin

Total nights spent by residents at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	627
1	98	1990	2015	71	19	1851
2	269	1990	2015	181	17	4706
3	0	0

3.10.33 tour_hap_pch_pre_tot Nights spent at Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, re

Total nights spent at hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by coun-try of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	620
1	98	1990	2015	69	18	1798
2	268	1990	2015	177	17	4612
3	0	0

3.10.34 tour_holacoth_bpl Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and tr

Holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of bed-places. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The number of bed places in a tourist accommodation establishment is determined by the number of persons who can stay overnight in the beds set up in the establishment, ignoring any extra beds that may be set up upon customer request. The term bed place applies to a single bed; a double bed is counted as two bed places.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	637
1	101	1990	2015	77	20	2006
2	276	1990	2015	200	19	5190
3	0	0

3.10.35 tour_holacoth_br Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and tr

Holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Bedrooms. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. A bedroom is the unit formed by one room or groups of rooms constituting an indivisible rental whole in an accommodation establishment or dwelling. Rooms may be single, double or multiple, depending on whether they are equipped permanently to accommodate one, two or several people (it is useful to classify the rooms respectively). The number of existing rooms is the number the establishment habitually has available to accommodate guests (overnight visitors), excluding rooms used by the employees working for the establishment. If a room is used as a permanent residence (for more than a year) it should not be included. Bathrooms and toilets do not count as a room. An apartment is a special type of room. It consists of one or more rooms and has a kitchen unit and its own bathroom and toilet. Apartments may be with hotel services (in apartment hotels) or without hotel services. Cabins, cottages, huts, chalets, bungalows and villas can be treated like bedrooms and apartments, i.e. to be let as a unit.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.36 tour_holacoth_nr_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping gr

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	643
1	101	1990	2015	74	19	1931
2	276	1990	2015	192	18	4982
3	0	0

3.10.37 tour_holacoth_nr_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping ground

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	645
1	101	1990	2015	75	19	1948
2	276	1990	2015	193	18	5025
3	0	0

3.10.38 tour_holacoth_nr_tot Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping gr

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	638
1	101	1990	2015	73	19	1906
2	276	1990	2015	190	18	4936
3	0	0

3.10.39 tour_holacoth_nre Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehicle parks and tr

Holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of establishments. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (al-though the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The local unit is an enterprise or part thereof situated in a geographically identified place. At or from this place economic activity is carried out for which - save for certain exceptions - one or more persons work (even if only part-time) for one and the same enterprise. The accommodation establishment conforms to the definition of local unit as the production unit. This is irrespective of whether the accommodation of tourists is the main or secondary activity. This means that all establishments are classified in the accommodation sector if their capacity exceeds the national minimum even if the major part of turnover may come from restaurant or other services.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	24	661
1	101	1990	2015	79	20	2051
2	276	1990	2015	203	19	5289
3	0	0

3.10.40 tour_holacoth_p_km2_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping gr

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.41 tour_holacoth_p_km2_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping ground

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.42 tour_holacoth_p_km2_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay ac-com.; camping grounds, recr. vehi

Total nights spent at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.43 tour_holacoth_p_thab_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping gr

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by coun-try of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.44 tour_holacoth_p_thab_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping ground

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by coun-try of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same

time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.45 tour_holacoth_p_thab_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay ac-com.; camping grounds, recr. vehi

Total nights spent at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.46 tour_holacoth_pc_tot_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping gr

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.47 tour_holacoth_pc_tot_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping ground

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.48 tour_holacoth_pc_tot_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay ac-com.; camping grounds, recr. vehi

Total nights spent at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.49 tour_holacoth_pch_pre_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping gr

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	626
1	98	1990	2015	70	19	1832
2	266	1990	2015	179	17	4650
3	0	0

3.10.50 tour_holacoth_pch_pre_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping ground

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	628
1	97	1990	2015	71	19	1843
2	266	1990	2015	181	18	4697
3	0	0

3.10.51 tour_holacoth_pch_pre_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehi

Total nights spent at holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accom-odation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	621
1	97	1990	2015	69	18	1787
2	265	1990	2015	177	17	4602
3	0	0

3.10.52 tour_hot_shstac_bpl Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehicle park

Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of bed-places. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The number of bed places in a tourist accommodation establishment is determined by the number of persons who can stay overnight in the beds set up in the establishment, ignoring any extra beds that may be set up upon customer request. The term bed place applies to a single bed; a double bed is counted as two bed places.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	23	633
1	101	1990	2015	72	19	1875
2	276	1990	2015	186	18	4842
3	0	0

3.10.53 tour_hot_shstac_br Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehicle park

Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Bedrooms. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. A bedroom is the unit formed by one room or groups of rooms constituting an indivisible rental whole in an accommodation establishment or dwelling. Rooms may be single, double or multiple, depending on whether they are equipped permanently to accommodate one, two or several people (it is useful to classify the rooms respectively). The number of existing rooms is the number the establishment habitually has available to accommodate guests (overnight visitors), excluding rooms used by the employees working for the establishment. If a room is used as a permanent residence (for more than a year) it should not be included. Bathrooms and toilets do not count as a room. An apartment is a special type of room. It consists of one or more rooms and has a kitchen unit and its own bathroom and toilet. Apartments may be with hotel services (in apartment hotels) or without hotel services. Cabins, cottages, huts, chalets, bungalows and villas can be treated like bedrooms and apartments, i.e. to be let as a unit.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.54 tour_hot_shstac_nre Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accom.; camping grounds, recr. vehicle park

Hotels; holiday and other short-stay accommodation; camping grounds, recreational vehicle parks and trailer parks, Number of establishments. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The local unit is an enterprise or part thereof situated in a geographically identified place. At or from this place economic activity is carried out for which - save for certain exceptions - one or more persons work (even if only part-time) for one and the same enterprise. The accommodation establishment conforms to the definition of local unit as the production unit. This is irrespective of whether the accommodation of tourists is the main or secondary activity. This means that all establishments are classified in the accommodation sector if their capacity exceeds the national minimum even if the major part of turnover may come from restaurant or other services.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	24	658
1	101	1990	2015	74	19	1928
2	276	1990	2015	190	18	4936
3	0	0

3.10.55 tour_hot_simac_bpl Hotels and similar accom., Number of bed-places

Hotels and similar accommodation, Number of bed-places. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The number of bed places in a tourist accommodation establishment is determined by the number of persons who can stay overnight in the beds set up in the establishment, ignoring any extra beds that may be set up upon customer request. The term bed place applies to a single bed; a double bed is counted as two bed places.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	26	24	679
1	101	1990	2015	78	20	2015
2	276	1990	2015	200	19	5192
3	0	0

3.10.56 tour_hot_simac_br Hotels and similar accom., Bedrooms

Hotels and similar accommodation, Bedrooms. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. A bedroom is the unit formed by one room or groups of rooms constituting an indivisible rental whole in an accommodation establishment or dwelling. Rooms may be single, double or multiple, depending on whether they are equipped permanently to accommodate one, two or several people (it is useful to classify the rooms respectively). The number of existing

rooms is the number the establishment habitually has available to accommodate guests (overnight visitors), excluding rooms used by the employees working for the establishment. If a room is used as a permanent residence (for more than a year) it should not be included. Bathrooms and toilets do not count as a room. An apartment is a special type of room. It consists of one or more rooms and has a kitchen unit and its own bathroom and toilet. Apartments may be with hotel services (in apartment hotels) or without hotel services. Cabins, cottages, huts, chalets, bungalows and villas can be treated like bedrooms and apartments, i.e. to be let as a unit.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	628
1	101	1990	2015	73	19	1888
2	276	1990	2015	189	18	4904
3	0	0

3.10.57 tour_hot_simac_nr_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels and similar accom. (Number)

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	26	24	669
1	101	1990	2015	81	21	2114
2	276	1990	2015	207	20	5390
3	0	0

3.10.58 tour_hot_simac_nr_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels and similar accom. (Number)

Total nights spent by residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another

country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	655
1	101	1990	2015	80	21	2088
2	276	1990	2015	208	20	5395
3	0	0

3.10.59 tour_hot_simac_nr_tot Nights spent at Hotels and similar accom. (Number)

Total nights spent at hotels and similar accommodation. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	650
1	101	1990	2015	80	21	2079
2	276	1990	2015	206	19	5359
3	0	0

3.10.60 tour_hot_simac_nre Hotels and similar accom., Number of establishments

Hotels and similar accommodation, Number of establishments. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The local unit is an enterprise or part thereof situated in a geographically identified place. At or from this place economic activity is carried out for which - save for certain exceptions - one or more persons work (even if only part-time) for one and the same enterprise. The accommodation establishment conforms to the definition of local unit as the production unit. This is irrespective of whether the accommodation of tourists is the main or secondary activity. This means that all establishments are classified in the accommodation sector if their capacity exceeds the national minimum even if the major part of turnover may come from restaurant or other services.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	26	24	680
1	101	1990	2015	78	20	2023
2	276	1990	2015	200	19	5207
3	0	0

3.10.61 tour_hot_simac_p_km2_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels and similar accom. (per square km)

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps

or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.62 tour_hot_simac_p_km2_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels and similar accom. (per square km)

Total nights spent by residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.63 tour_hot_simac_p_km2_tot Nights spent at Hotels and similar accom. (per square km)

Total nights spent at hotels and similar accommodation. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the

date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.64 tour_hot_simac_p_thab_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels and similar accom. (per 1000 inh.)

Total nights spent by residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.65 tour_hot_simac_p_thab_tot Nights spent at Hotels and similar accom. (per 1000 inh.)

Total nights spent at hotels and similar accommodation. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.66 tour_hot_simac_pc_tot_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels and similar accom. (% of total)

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.67 tour_hot_simac_pc_tot_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels and similar accom. (% of total)

Total nights spent by residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.68 tour_hot_simac_pc_tot_tot Nights spent at Hotels and similar accom. (% of total)

Total nights spent at hotels and similar accommodation. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.69 tour_hot_simac_pch_pre_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels and similar accom. (% change over prev.

Total nights spent by non-residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	651
1	98	1990	2015	78	21	2033
2	272	1990	2015	196	19	5107
3	0	0

3.10.70 tour_hot_simac_pch_pre_r Nights spent by residents at Hotels and similar accom. (% change over prev. peri

Total nights spent by residents at hotels and similar accommodation. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12

months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	25	23	638
1	98	1990	2015	77	20	2000
2	272	1990	2015	197	19	5112
3	0	0

3.10.71 tour_hot_simac_pch_pre_tot Nights spent at Hotels and similar accom. (% change over prev. period)

Total nights spent at hotels and similar accommodation. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	23	631
1	98	1990	2015	76	20	1976
2	272	1990	2015	195	19	5073
3	0	0

3.10.72 tour_hot_simacp_thab_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Hotels and similar accom. (per 1000 inh.)

Total nights spent at hotels and similar accommodation. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.73 tour_hssc_bpl Holiday and other short-stay accom., Number of bed-places

Holiday and other short-stay accommodation, Number of bed-places. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is

reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The number of bed places in a tourist accommodation establishment is determined by the number of persons who can stay overnight in the beds set up in the establishment, ignoring any extra beds that may be set up upon customer request. The term bed place applies to a single bed; a double bed is counted as two bed places.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	23	22	603
1	101	1990	2015	77	20	1998
2	276	1990	2015	199	19	5164
3	0	0

3.10.74 tour_hssc_br Holiday and other short-stay accom., Bedrooms

Holiday and other short-stay accommodation, Bedrooms. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommodation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. A bedroom is the unit formed by one room or groups of rooms constituting an indivisible rental whole in an accommodation establishment or dwelling. Rooms may be single, double or multiple, depending on whether they are equipped permanently to accommodate one, two or several people (it is useful to classify the rooms respectively). The number of existing rooms is the number the establishment habitually has available to accommodate guests (overnight visitors), excluding rooms used by the employees working for the establishment. If a room is used as a permanent residence (for more than a year) it should not be included. Bathrooms and toilets do not count as a room. An apartment is a special type of room. It consists of one or more rooms and has a kitchen unit and its own bathroom and toilet. Apartments may be with hotel services (in apartment hotels) or without hotel services. Cabins, cottages, huts, chalets, bungalows and villas can be treated like bedrooms and apartments, i.e. to be let as a unit.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.75 tour_hssc_nr_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (Number)

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	22	21	576
1	101	1990	2015	63	16	1634
2	276	1990	2015	162	15	4218
3	0	0

3.10.76 tour_hssc_nr_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (Number)

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	22	21	580
1	101	1990	2015	64	16	1658
2	276	1990	2015	165	16	4288
3	0	0

3.10.77 tour_hssc_nr_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (Number)

Total nights spent at at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Number. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	22	20	569
1	101	1990	2015	63	16	1628
2	276	1990	2015	161	15	4196
3	0	0

3.10.78 tour_hssc_nre Holiday and other short-stay accom., Number of establish-ments

Holiday and other short-stay accommodation, Number of establishments. A tourist accommodation establishment is defined as any facility that regularly or occasionally provides short-term accommo-dation for tourists as a paid service (although the price might be partially or fully subsidised). Data is reported at the level of a local kind-of-activity unit. The local unit is an enterprise or part thereof situated in a geographically identified place. At or from this place economic activity is carried out for which - save for certain exceptions - one or more persons work (even if only part-time) for one and the same enterprise. The accommodation establishment conforms to the definition of local unit as the production unit. This is irrespective of whether the accommodation of tourists is the main or secondary activity. This means that all establishments are classified in the accommodation sector if their capacity exceeds the national minimum even if the major part of turnover may come from restaurant or other services.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	24	22	613
1	101	1990	2015	77	20	2011
2	276	1990	2015	200	19	5195
3	0	0

3.10.79 tour_hssc_p_km2_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (per square

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.80 tour_hssc_p_km2_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (per square km)

Total nights spent by residents at at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving

on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.81 tour_hssc_p_km2_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (per square km)

Total nights spent at at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.82 tour_hssc_p_thab_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (per 1000 i

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Per km2. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.83 tour_hssc_p_thab_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (per 1000 inh.)

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.84 tour_hssc_p_thab_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (per 1000 inh.)

Total nights spent at at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Per thousand inhabitants. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.85 tour_hssc_pc_tot_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (% of total)

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.86 tour_hssc_pc_tot_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (% of total)

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.87 tour_hssc_pc_tot_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (% of total)

Total nights spent at at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Percentage of total. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.10.88 tour_hssc_pch_pre_nr Nights spent by non-residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (% change o

Total nights spent by non-residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12 months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	21	20	548
1	98	1990	2015	58	15	1500
2	266	1990	2015	148	14	3837
3	0	0

3.10.89 tour_hssc_pch_pre_r Nights spent by residents at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (% change over

Total nights spent by residents at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time. A person is considered to be a resident in a country (place) if the person: has lived for most of the past year or 12 months in that country (place), or has lived in that country (place) for a shorter period and intends to return within 12

months to live in that country (place). International tourists should be classified according to their country of residence, not according to their citizenship. From a tourism standpoint any person who moves to another country (place) and intends to stay there for more than one year is immediately assimilated with other residents of that country (place). Citizens residing abroad who return to their country of citizenship on a temporary visit are included with non-resident visitors. Citizenship is indicated in the person's passport (or other identification document), while country of residence has to be determined by means of question or inferred e.g. from the person's address.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	21	20	553
1	98	1990	2015	59	16	1523
2	267	1990	2015	150	15	3893
3	0	0

3.10.90 tour_hssc_pch_pre_tot Nights spent at Holiday and other short-stay accom. (% change over prev. period)

Total nights spent at at holiday and other short-stay accommodation. Percentage change over previous period. A night spent (or overnight stay) is each night a guest / tourist (resident or non-resident) actually spends (sleeps or stays) in a tourist accommodation establishment or non-rented accommodation. Overnight stays are calculated by country of residence of the guest and by month. Normally the date of arrival is different from the date of departure but persons arriving after midnight and leaving on the same day are included in overnight stays. A person should not be registered in two or more accommodation establishments at the same time.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2015	21	19	540
1	98	1991	2015	60	15	1492
2	266	1991	2015	152	14	3801
3	0	0

3.11 Eurostat: Transport Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-17)

Eurostat: Transport Statistics Regional transport statistics aim to quantify the flows of passengers and freight between, within and through regions; differences between regions are often closely related to levels of economic activity. Transport statistics are also collected for a range of other indicators, for example, in relation to transport infrastructure (the length of transport networks) and equipment rates (the number of vehicles per inhabitant). Regional data on road infrastructure and vehicle stocks are currently collected by EU Member States, EFTA and candidate countries on a voluntary basis.

3.11.1 tr_cnl_km Navigable canals (kilometre)

Navigable canal Ū waterway built primarily for navigation.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	18	1990	2013	15	21	369
1	63	1990	2013	45	17	1089
2	140	1990	2013	86	15	2069
3	0	0

3.11.2 tr_cnl_tkm2 Navigable canals (kilometre/1000 square km)
 Navigable canal Ū waterway built primarily for navigation.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.11.3 tr_fr_ld Maritime transport, freight loaded (1000's tonnes)

Maritime transport, freight loaded (1000's tonnes). The maritime transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the port level in the frame of Council Directive 2009/42/EC (6.5.2009). They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	23	1997	2013	20	15	335
1	67	1997	2013	56	14	948
2	135	1997	2013	115	14	1947
3	0	0

3.11.4 tr_fr_ld_nld Maritime transport, freight loaded and unloaded (1000's tonnes)

Maritime transport, freight loaded and unloaded (1000's tonnes). The maritime transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the port level in the frame of Council Directive 2009/42/EC (6.5.2009). They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	23	1997	2013	20	15	335
1	68	1997	2013	56	14	950
2	137	1997	2013	115	14	1950
3	0	0

3.11.6 tr_fr_nld Maritime transport, freight unloaded (1000's tonnes)

Maritime transport, freight unloaded (1000's tonnes). The maritime transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the port level in the frame of Council Directive 2009/42/EC (6.5.2009). They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	23	1997	2013	20	15	335
1	67	1997	2013	56	14	949
2	136	1997	2013	115	14	1947
3	0	0

3.11.6 tr_frm_Id Air transport, freight and mail loaded (1000's tonnes)

Air transport, freight and mail loaded (1000's tonnes). The air transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the airport level in the frame of Commission Regulation (EC) No 1358/2003. They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1993	2013	20	15	422
1	99	1993	2013	75	16	1577
2	220	1993	2013	153	15	3219
3	0	0

3.11.7 tr_frm_nld Air transport, freight and mail unloaded (1000's tonnes)

Air transport, freight and mail unloaded (1000's tonnes). The air transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the airport level in the frame of Commission Regulation (EC) No 1358/2003. They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1993	2013	20	15	422
1	100	1993	2013	76	16	1598
2	222	1993	2013	156	15	3271
3	0	0

3.11.8 tr_Id_nld Air transport, freight and mail loaded and unloaded (1000's tonnes)

Air transport, freight and mail loaded and unloaded (1000's tonnes). The air transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the airport level in the frame of Commission Regulation (EC) No 1358/2003. They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1993	2013	20	15	422
1	100	1993	2013	76	16	1603
2	222	1993	2013	157	15	3296
3	0	0

3.11.9 tr_mway_km Motorways (kilometre)

Data on motorways network at regional level, kilometre

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2013	25	22	601
1	97	1990	2013	90	22	2162
2	271	1990	2013	213	19	5102
3	0	0

3.11.10 tr_mway_tkm2 Motorways (kilometre/1000 square km)

Data on motorways network at regional level , kilometre/1000 square km.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	27	1990	2013	25	22	601
1	97	1990	2013	90	22	2162
2	271	1990	2013	213	19	5103
3	0	0

3.11.11 tr_pas Maritime transport, passengers embarked and disembarked (1000's)

Maritime transport, passengers embarked and disembarked (1000's). The maritime transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the port level in the frame of Council Directive 2009/42/EC (6.5.2009). They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	23	1997	2013	19	14	328
1	66	1997	2013	52	13	885
2	125	1997	2013	93	13	1581
3	0	0

3.11.12 tr_pas_crd Air transport, passengers departures and arrivals (1000's)

Air transport, passengers departures and arrivals (1000's). The air transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the airport level in the frame of Commission Regulation (EC) No 1358/2003. They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1993	2013	21	16	450
1	101	1993	2013	80	17	1674
2	228	1993	2013	169	16	3553
3	0	0

3.11.13 tr_pas_crd_arr Air transport, passengers arrivals (1000's)

Air transport, passengers arrivals (1000's). The air transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the airport level in the frame of Commission Regulation (EC) No 1358/2003. They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1993	2013	21	16	450
1	101	1993	2013	80	17	1674
2	227	1993	2013	169	16	3547
3	0	0

3.11.14 tr_pas_crd_dep Air transport, passengers departures (1000's)

Air transport, passengers departures (1000's). The air transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the airport level in the frame of Commission Regulation (EC) No 1358/2003. They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1993	2013	21	16	450
1	100	1993	2013	79	17	1666
2	225	1993	2013	168	16	3528
3	0	0

3.11.15 tr_pas_demb Maritime transport, passengers disembarked (1000's)

Maritime transport, passengers disembarked (1000's). The maritime transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the port level in the frame of Council Directive 2009/42/EC (6.5.2009). They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	23	1997	2013	19	14	328
1	66	1997	2013	52	13	882
2	125	1997	2013	93	13	1575
3	0	0

3.11.16 tr_pas_emb Maritime transport, passengers embarked (1000's)

Maritime transport, passengers embarked (1000's). The maritime transport regional data have been calculated using data collected at the port level in the frame of Council Directive 2009/42/EC (6.5.2009). They are aggregated at regional level (NUTS 1 and NUTS 2) and also at national level (NUTS0), excluding double counting within each region.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	23	1997	2013	19	14	328
1	66	1997	2013	51	13	874
2	125	1997	2013	92	12	1557
3	0	0

3.11.17 tr_rd_oth_km Other roads (kilometre)

Other roads (kilometre)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1990	2013	24	21	577
1	98	1990	2013	86	21	2053
2	269	1990	2013	200	18	4793
3	0	0

3.11.18 tr_rd_oth_tkm2 Other roads (kilometre/1000 square km)
Other roads (kilometre/1000 square km)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.11.19 tr_riv_km Navigable rivers (kilometre)

Navigable rivers (kilometre). Navigable river ũ natural waterway open for navigation, irrespective of whether it has been improved for that purpose.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	21	1990	2013	17	20	414
1	68	1990	2013	51	18	1212
2	138	1990	2013	69	12	1645
3	0	0

3.11.20 tr_riv_tkm2 Navigable rivers (kilometre/1000 square km)

Navigable rivers (kilometre/1000 square km). Navigable river ũ natural waterway open for navigation, irrespective of whether it has been improved for that purpose.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.11.21 tr_rl_elc_km Electrified railway lines (kilometre)

Electrified railway lines (kilometre)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1990	2013	24	22	565
1	84	1990	2013	55	16	1315
2	191	1990	2013	127	16	3057
3	0	0

3.11.22 tr_rl_elc_tkm2 Electrified railway lines (kilometre/1000 square km)

Electrified railway lines (kilometre/1000 square km)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.11.23 tr_rl_km Total railway lines (kilometre)

Total railway lines(electrified and non-electrified) , Kilometre.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1990	2013	25	23	589
1	84	1990	2013	60	17	1444
2	191	1990	2013	137	17	3282
3	0	0

3.11.24 tr_rl_tge2_km Railway lines with double and more tracks (kilometre)

Railway lines (electrified and non-electrified) with double and more tracks (kilometre)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	26	1990	2013	23	21	545
1	82	1990	2013	51	15	1217
2	191	1990	2013	126	16	3027
3	0	0

3.11.25 tr_rl_tge2_tkm2 Railway lines with double and more tracks (kilometre/1000 square km)

Railway lines (electrified and non-electrified) with double and more tracks (kilometre/1000 square km)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

3.11.26 tr_rl_tkm2 Total railway lines (kilometre/1000 square km)

Total railway lines (electrified and non-electrified), (kilometre/1000 square km)

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	0	0
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0

0	26	1990	2013	25	23	589
1	84	1990	2013	60	17	1444
2	191	1990	2013	137	17	3282
3	0	0

3.12 Eurostat: Labour Market Statistics

(Data downloaded: 2016-03-17)

Eurostat: Labour Market Statistics An unemployed person is defined by Eurostat, according to the guidelines of the International Labour Organization, as someone aged 15 to 74 without work during the reference week who is available to start work within the next two weeks and who has actively sought employment at some time during the last four weeks. The unemployment rate is the number of people unemployed as a percentage of the labour force. In addition to the unemployment measures covered here, Eurostat also publishes statistics for persons who fulfil only partially the definition of unemployment. These persons are not included in the official ILO unemployment concept and have a varying degree of attachment to the labour market. The indicators on underemployment and potential additional labour force participants supplement the unemployment rate to provide a more complete picture of the labour market.

3.12.1 unemp_pc_act Long-term unemployment (% of active population)

The share of long-term unemployment is the share of unemployed persons since 12 months or more in the total active population, expressed as a percentage. The total active population (labour force) is the total number of the employed and unemployed population. The duration of unemployment is defined as the duration of a search for a job or as the period of time since the last job was held (if this period is shorter than the duration of the search for a job).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	27	16	438
1	100	1999	2014	94	15	1501
2	273	1999	2014	232	14	3708
3	0	0

3.12.2 unemp_pc_une Long-term unemployment (% of unemployment)

The share of long-term unemployment is the share of unemployed persons since 12 months or more in the unemployed population, expressed as a percentage. The duration of unemployment is defined as the duration of a search for a job or as the period of time since the last job was held (if this period is shorter than the duration of the search for a job).

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	27	16	438
1	100	1999	2014	94	15	1501
2	273	1999	2014	232	14	3708
3	0	0

3.12.3 unemp_y1524_f Unemployment rates: 15-24 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 15-24 Years, Female ,%. Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	95	15	1515
2	276	1999	2014	251	15	4019
3	0	0

3.12.4 unemp_y1524_m Unemployment rates: 15-24 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 15-24 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1532
2	279	1999	2014	257	15	4106
3	0	0

3.12.5 unemp_y1524_t Unemployment rates: 15-24 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 15-24 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1538
2	279	1999	2014	261	15	4175
3	0	0

3.12.6 unemp_y1564_f Unemployment rates: 15-64 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 15-64 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4206
3	0	0

3.12.7 unemp_y1564_m Unemployment rates: 15-64 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 15-64 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.8 unemp_y1564_t Unemployment rates: 15-64 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 15-64 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.9 unemp_y2064_f Unemployment rates: 20-64 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 20-64 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4206
3	0	0

3.12.10 unemp_y2064_m Unemployment rates: 20-64 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 20-64 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3.

actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.11 unemp_y2064_t Unemployment rates: 20-64 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 20-64 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.12 unemp_y2534_f Unemployment rates: 25-34 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 25-34 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1538
2	279	1999	2014	261	15	4181
3	0	0

3.12.13 unemp_y2534_m Unemployment rates: 25-34 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 25-34 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1538
2	279	1999	2014	261	15	4180
3	0	0

3.12.14 unemp_y2534_t Unemployment rates: 25-34 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 25-34 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4204
3	0	0

3.12.15 unemp_y2564_f Unemployment rates: 25-64 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 25-64 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4206
3	0	0

3.12.16 unemp_y2564_m Unemployment rates: 25-64 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 25-64 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.17 unemp_y2564_t Unemployment rates: 25-64 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 25-64 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.18 unemp_y3544_f Unemployment rates: 35-44 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 35-44 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1538
2	279	1999	2014	261	15	4183
3	0	0

3.12.19 unemp_y3544_m Unemployment rates: 35-44 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 35-44 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1538
2	279	1999	2014	262	15	4187
3	0	0

3.12.20 unemp_y3544_t Unemployment rates: 35-44 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 35-44 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4204
3	0	0

3.12.21 unemp_y4554_f Unemployment rates: 45-54 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 45-54 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1533
2	279	1999	2014	260	15	4167
3	0	0

3.12.22 unemp_y4554_m Unemployment rates: 45-54 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 45-54 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	96	15	1538
2	279	1999	2014	262	15	4186
3	0	0

3.12.23 unemp_y4554_t Unemployment rates: 45-54 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 45-54 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4206
3	0	0

3.12.24 unemp_y5564_f Unemployment rates: 55-64 Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 55-64 Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	99	1999	2014	95	15	1516
2	278	1999	2014	253	15	4054
3	0	0

3.12.25 unemp_y5564_m Unemployment rates: 55-64 Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 55-64 Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	100	1999	2014	95	15	1526
2	279	1999	2014	258	15	4131
3	0	0

3.12.26 unemp_y5564_t Unemployment rates: 55-64 Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 55-64 Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1549
2	280	1999	2014	262	15	4188
3	0	0

3.12.27 unemp_yge15_f Unemployment rates: 15+ Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 15+ Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4206
3	0	0

3.12.28 unemp_yge15_m Unemployment rates: 15+ Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 15+ Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.29 unemp_yge15_t Unemployment rates: 15+ Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 15+ Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.30 unemp_yge25_f Unemployment rates: 25+ Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 25+ Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4206
3	0	0

3.12.31 unemp_yge25_m Unemployment rates: 25+ Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 25+ Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.32 unemp_yge25_t Unemployment rates: 25+ Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 25+ Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	28	16	443
1	101	1999	2014	97	15	1554
2	280	1999	2014	263	15	4208
3	0	0

3.12.33 unemp_yge65_f Unemployment rates: 65+ Years, FeMale

Unemployment Rates: 65+ Years, Female ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	26	15	411
1	92	1999	2014	73	13	1172
2	209	1999	2014	123	9	1970
3	0	0

3.12.34 unemp_yge65_m Unemployment rates: 65+ Years, Male

Unemployment Rates: 65+ Years, Male ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	27	15	430
1	96	1999	2014	83	14	1335
2	242	1999	2014	172	11	2759
3	0	0

3.12.35 unemp_yge65_t Unemployment rates: 65+ Years, Total

Unemployment Rates: 65+ Years, Total ,%.Regional unemployment rate represents unemployed persons as a percentage of the economically active population (i.e. labour force or sum of employed and unemployed). The indicator is based on the EU Labour Force Survey. Unemployed persons comprise persons aged 15-74 who were (all three conditions must be fulfilled simultaneously): 1. without work during the reference week; 2. currently available for work; 3. actively seeking work or who had found a job to start within a period of at most three months.

Descriptive variable statistics

NUTS Level	N	Min. Years	Max. Years	Ave. N	Ave. Years	n
0	28	1999	2014	27	15	433
1	99	1999	2014	88	14	1410
2	265	1999	2014	202	12	3227
3	0	0

3.13 EU Structural Fund Data

3.13.1 Regional Variables on EU Structural Funds

The purpose of these variables is to provide the overall influence of EU Structural Funds (SF's) in EU regions, whereby estimates of annual SF's expenditures to regions are provided here. All raw data are taken from the EU Regional Policy's webpage 'Data for Research'¹. As the rules and make up of Cohesion funds change with each budget period, each budget period was collected and organized separately, starting from 2000. In all, data have been collected annually from 2000-2013, with the 2014-2020 period collected in the aggregate for each region.

For the 2000-2006 period, the SF's included European Social Fund (ESF), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the Financial Instrument for Fisheries Guidance (FIFG), and the European Agricultural Guidance and Guarantee Fund (EAGGF). Funds fall under Objective 1, 2 and 3, as well as 'Community Initiative Programmes'. During this period, data are collected in four categories – cohesion objective (regional operating programme, 'OP'), competitiveness objective (regional OP), cohesion objective (national OP), competitiveness objective (national OP)

For the 2007-2013 budget period, the SF's included European Social Fund (ESF), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), and the Cohesion Fund (CF). Data during this period are collected into six categories – objective 1-3 within regional OP's, and objective 1-3 within national OP's.

For the 2014-2020 budget period, the SF's included European Social Fund (ESF), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund (CF). Rural Development Funds (EAFRD) and Maritime and Fisheries funding (EMFF) are also collected, and are added to a separate variable line. Data within this period are collected into seven categories – SF with a regional OP within ERDF and ESF, SF with a regional OP within EARDF and EMFF, national OP SF's more developed, transition and less developed within ERDF and ESF, national OP SF's within EARRD and EMFF, and other national OP SFs.

It is worth noting that in none of the budget periods are the cross-border ('inter-regional') expenditures included, as we did not have specific enough information regarding exactly how much each region/area received to assign these SFs with any confident precision. These funds are generally about 2.5% of the total SF budget.

In order to increase valid comparisons over time, the data are collected at the NUTS 2 level in most all cases, and NUTS 1 in two exceptions, where NUTS 2 estimates less reliable (Greece) or relevant (Germany). Yet in these cases, we also provide per capita expenditures (estimates) for the NUTS 2 level regions. For smaller countries with only 1 NUTS 2 level region (Malta, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Latvia, Estonia and Lithuania), the national level expenditures are provided.

With these data collected, we build the following four variables:

3.13.2 - SF_reg

total annual SF expenditures in a region (estimate) within the region's Operating Programme (OP). Countries without specified regional OP's take a value of '0'. In the case of the 2014-2020 budget period, this variable does not include budget items that fall under the EMFF and EARDF within the regional OP. In cases where regions do not have their own OP, the cell is left blank rather than imputing a '0' so as to not underestimate total spending.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/evaluations/data-for-research/

3.13.3 - SF_reg_pc

total annual SF expenditures in a region (estimate) within the region's OP 'SF_reg_op_only' divided over a region's total population for the same year (from Eurostat).

3.13.4 - SF_total

The total annual SF expenditures in a region (estimate) from the combined regional OP and national OP. To estimate national OP expenditures in a region, we allocate these Funds proportionally to the each region in terms of population size. For example, if region 'x' is 25% of the total population in country 'z', then 25% of the Funds in a given national OP would be assigned to region 'x', and so on. This is added to the expenditures via the regional OP in applicable cases (SF_reg_op_only).

Two issues arises with this estimation technique that requires us to make certain assumptions about geographic allocation of Funds. First, some countries have 'uniform regions' (Bulgaria, Sweden in 2007-2013) where all regions fall under the same objective category (for example, objective 1, 'competitiveness', etc), and in this case, Funds from national OPs are allocated evenly to regions in terms of population proportion for each year. While we cannot be 100% sure that these Funds are in fact allocated evenly (by population proportion) to each region, it is our 'best guess', and thus the estimates should be treated with some caution. In other cases, countries have regions that fall into different Cohesion goals (for example Italy's Northern regions versus the Mezzogiorno, or Slovakia with Bratislava region falling under 'more developed' and the other three NUTS 2 regions being 'less developed'). In this case, we take advantage of the stated objective goal included in each budget line of the national OP and allocated these funds proportionally (based on within-group regional population) to those regions that fall under that stated goal.

For example, in the 2014-2020 budget period, Funds are specified as 'less developed', 'transition' and 'more developed'. Thus for example, in the case of Italy, for all Funds are spent through national OPs for 'less developed' areas, we allocate those Funds only to regions that are classified as 'less developed'. To do so, we take the sum population of all regions in each category and take the proportion of each region's population within this category, and assign it equal proportion of Funds from national OPs within this objective group. Thus, if the region of Campania is 33% of the total population of the regions within the 'less developed' group in Italy, Campania would be assigned 33% of the national OP Funds going toward 'less developed' areas, and so on.

Second, the Cohesion Fund (CF) expenditures, which were more or less fully integrated into the Structural funds from the 2007-2013 budgets onward, are allocated to countries below the 90% level of the EU average of GDP per capita (PPP), and are thus not regional programs, but national ones. These CF Funds where applicable are in all cases divided evenly to each region based on population proportion. Therefore, in some cases there will be some 'accidental winners' of this method, (e.g. wealthy regions in poor countries, such as Prague, or Bratislava). Again, while we cannot be sure if these Funds are in fact spread evenly throughout the country, it is our 'best guess' until we obtain evidence otherwise.

3.13.5 - SF_total_pc

The total annual SF expenditures in a region (estimate) within the region's OP plus National OP 'SF_total' divided over a region's total population for the same year (from Eurostat).

3.13.6 - Objective1_r

a dummy variable coded as '1' if a region falls under 'objective 1' status (2000-2006 parlance), 'cohesion' status (2007-2013 parlance) or 'less developed' status (2014-2020 parlance) and '0' if otherwise.

**These five variables are located ONLY in the file 'PERCEIVE Regional Dataset NUTS2.dta'*

*In addition to the annual data we provide in the panel data file, we also provide total Structural Fund expenditures by the latest three Budget periods (2000-2006, 2007-2013 and 2014-2020) by region. In addition, we estimate all per capita spending at the NUTS 2 level (including Germany and Greece). This excel file also includes the following two variables:

3.13.7 - SF_total_extra_14_20

Available for the 2014-2020 budget period data (see Excel file), whereby the regional and national level expenditures for the EARFD and EMFF are added to the Structural Fund expenditures.

3.13.8 - SF_total_extra_14_20pc

Available for the 2014-2020 budget period data (see Excel file), whereby the regional and national level expenditures for the EARFD and EMFF are added to the Structural Fund expenditures, divided over a region's total population for the same year (from Eurostat).

4. References and Sources

1. Eurostat data - <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/about/policies/copyright>

2. Data on Quality of government:

Charron, N., Dijkstra, L., & Lapuente, V. (2014). Regional governance matters: quality of government within European Union member states. *Regional Studies*, 48(1), 68-90.

Charron, N., Dijkstra, L., & Lapuente, V. (2015). Mapping the regional divide in Europe: A measure for assessing quality of government in 206 European regions. *Social Indicators Research*, 122(2), 315-346.

3. Data on Structural Funds – ‘data for researchers’ page, EU Commission

http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/evaluations/data-for-research/